

D8.1 Communication & Dissemination strategy

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Deliverable information sheet

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Executive summary

Shift2Zero, Shifting to zero-emission logistics through right-sized, mission-focused, N1 e-LCVs

Shift2Zero, Shifting to zero-emission logistics through right-sized, mission-focused, N1 e-LCVs Current market dynamics in EU reveal a gap between supply - existing N1 vehicles, and demand - evolving needs of urban logistics and climate targets. In 2023, 1.2M new LCV registrations were diesel-powered, and only 108,200 battery electric. Last-mile logistics, the least efficient and most complex part of the supply chain, presents significant opportunities for improvements at vehicle and operations levels. Dynamic requirements and increasing environmental impact require innovative solutions from the automotive industry, both from high volume OEMs and new entrants. S2Z aims to capitalize on the benefits of both vehicle platforms in the N1 segment - represented by IVECO's eDaily multipurpose platform, and Alke's ATX design-for-purpose platform - ultimately contributing to "Shifting to zero-emission logistics through right-sized, mission-focused, N1 e-LCVs".

To achieve this vision, S2Z proposes a 4-step user- and mission-centric design approach placing end-users and their needs at the core of all project activities. To this end, S2Z involves 5 LSPs & mobility operators as partners: Gruber, DHL, Diakinisis, Clem, DPD. As a result, S2Z will co-develop and shape at least 6 novel N1 concepts with enhanced and safe functionalities leading to tighter market fit, particularly in the segments of e-commerce, returns and cold deliveries.

Innovative concepts, from modular cargo bodies to vehicle control strategies with optimized tyres & brakes, as well as dual transport of people & freight, will be physically prototyped and tested in real-life operations in 6 pilot sites (Belgium, Greece, Italy, 2 in Norway, Poland).

S2Z brings a multidisciplinary consortium of 30 partners from 10 countries to cover the complete automotive and logistics value chains, complemented by policymakers to effectively ensure route to market: overcoming barriers for the adoption of S2Z eLCVs, reducing operational costs and environmental impact in scalable urban & sub-urban operations.

This deliverable **D8.1** outlines the **Communication, Dissemination and Clustering (CDC)** strategy of the Shift2Zero project, with the aim of maximising outreach, rising awareness, engaging stakeholders, and ensuring the lasting impact of the project results beyond its completion. This strategy identifies target audiences, channels, key

messages, activities, timelines and guidelines for the effective implementation of the CDC strategy.

Eurecat (EUT), with the collaboration of BAX as WP leader, will lead communication, dissemination and clustering tasks (T8.1 and ST8.3.3) with all partners contribution to the successful execution of the plan.

- **Communication:** from the outset of the project, communication activities have been launched and will continue beyond the conclusion of Shift2Zero. T8.1 includes the creation of various visual materials to support outreach efforts, including visual guidelines, templates, and compelling communication resources. Media relations, the publication and maintenance of the public project website, the production of audiovisual content, and stakeholder engagement through participation in relevant non-specialist events are also key components of the communication strategy.
- **Dissemination:** the efforts and actions related to dissemination aspects will begin as soon as the initial project results are available for sharing. In this sense, T8.1 includes a comprehensive approach to academic and industrial dissemination, with activities such as participation in scientific and industrial conferences, organising workshops, training actions, and public events. Additionally, scientific papers will be published and a community of interest around the project will be created.
- **Clustering:** these activities initiated at M2 by establishing some contacts and synergies with various projects and EU associations / initiatives. Clustering actions will increase in next months and will focus on building a network within the logistics innovation community. These actions will include the exchange of project achievements and participation in common outreach efforts with related EU initiatives.

All CDC activities will be continuously monitored and updated throughout the project's lifecycle, facilitated by dedicated tracking tools, including Excels template for communication and dissemination activities, as well as to track key performance indicators (KPIs). This monitoring process will be essential to assess progress toward CDC goals and to refine the strategy as needed based on lessons learned throughout the project.

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>CDC</i>	<i>Communication, Dissemination and Clustering</i>
<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>e-LCV</i>	<i>Electric Light Commercial Vehicle</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>LSPs</i>	<i>Logistics Service Providers</i>
<i>S2Z</i>	<i>Shift2Zero</i>
<i>TG</i>	<i>Target Group</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Introduction

Shift2Zero is a 42-month European project developing **innovative and mission-focused N1 e-LCVs designs and functionalities** that **enhance efficiency, reduce emissions, and align with evolving logistics requirements**.

EUT is the leader of **Task 8.1 Communication and Dissemination** and **Subtask 8.3.3 Clustering activities and Stakeholder Advisory Board**, which are related to the present deliverable. EUT is responsible for defining the project's Communication, Dissemination and Clustering (CDC) plan.

This document outlines the Shift2Zero CDC strategy, including target audiences, activity goals, and methods for monitoring and evaluation.

All the actions in the plan have been defined taking into consideration the European Research Executive Agency's recommendations and guidelines for European-funded research and innovation projects¹.

1.1 Objectives and structure of the deliverable

The main goal of this deliverable is to outline the strategy for effectively communicating the project, engaging with targeted stakeholders, disseminating its results, and collaborating with related initiatives.

This document serves as a guideline for implementing communication, dissemination and clustering activities, following a strategy designed to achieve the specific objectives outlined within it. EUT will monitor the results of the CDC actions based on the procedures established in this document and will adjust the plan as needed to meet the targeted KPIs.

All partners are expected to refer to this document when carrying out any CDC activity, as it aims to standardise and unify all communication and dissemination efforts across the project.

The deliverable is structured along with the following sections:

- **Section 2: Communication, Dissemination, and Clustering plan objectives** — This section lays the foundation for Shift2Zero's CDC strategy by:
 - Identifying key stakeholders who are the primary targets for dissemination and communication efforts.
 - Developing key messages tailored to the interests and needs of each stakeholder group, ensuring a consistent and effective engagement approach.
- **Section 3: Communication, Dissemination, and Clustering Plan management** — This section outlines the governance structure of the CDC strategy by:
 - Defining the roles and responsibilities of EUT (task leader), BAX (WP leader), and all project partners.
 - Establishing key requirements to guide partners in carrying out communication, dissemination and clustering activities.

¹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en

- Detailing how essential aspects such as ethics, gender equality, and inclusivity will be integrated into the development and execution of the CDC strategy.
- Presenting a monitoring and reporting framework to track progress toward CDC objectives, capture key lessons learned throughout the project, and refine the strategy as needed.
 - Identifying potential risks that could impact CDC activities and proposing mitigation measures to address them proactively.
- **Section 4: Communication** — This section outlines the communication strategy and action plan aimed at raising awareness and maximising the project’s visibility.
- **Section 5: Dissemination** — This section describes the approach for sharing the project’s findings and knowledge with relevant audiences through various channels, such as conferences, trade fairs, events, scientific publications, and training initiatives.
- **Section 6: Clustering** — This section outlines the strategy for clustering activities, aimed at fostering collaboration with related initiatives and projects. It focuses on creating synergies and leveraging collective knowledge and resources to enhance the impact of Shift2Zero’s results.

2. Communication, dissemination and clustering objectives

The main goals of the Shift2Zero project communication, dissemination and clustering strategy are:

1. **Increase the global visibility of Shift2Zero and its outcomes in Europe and beyond:** leveraging a variety of communication channels, including social media, scientific publications, press releases, webinars, and conferences, to reach both European and global audiences. By strategically collaborating with other initiatives and projects through clustering, Shift2Zero will amplify its visibility, ensuring that its key findings and achievements reach a wide range of stakeholders across the globe.
2. **Develop novel communication and dissemination activities to facilitate knowledge transfer to scientific and industry stakeholders:** the CDC strategy will employ targeted tools and channels tailored to specific audiences, such as industry stakeholders, policymakers, and the scientific community.
3. **Raise awareness on the project, its funding and its economic and environmental impact in the European logistics and mobility sectors:** the project will use a wide range of communication tools to increase awareness of the project’s funding sources, goals, and the significant environmental and economic impact it aims to achieve in the European logistics and mobility sectors. Dissemination activities will focus on engaging key stakeholders through trade fairs, industry events, and scientific publications.

It is worth noting that to protect the commercial interests of the partners, the publication of the materials will be selective, except for submission of contractually required reports and information to the Commission. In this case, partners decide which part of the projects’ information is to be protected by copyright or trade secrets and which part of the information is suitable for disseminating widely.

All the actions in the plan consider the European Commission’s recommendations and guidelines for Horizon Europe research and innovation projects².

2.1 Target of communication, dissemination and clustering

A preliminary analysis of the target audiences for dissemination has been conducted, identifying four key stakeholder groups: academia, industry, end-users/customers, policymakers, and the general public. Dissemination and communication activities will be designed to meet the needs and interests of these TGs and amplify the impact of the project.

A detailed overview is provided in *Figure 1*.

Industry	Academia	Policy makers	EU society
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility fleet managers • Logistics services providers & mobility operators • Logistics chain (retailers, supermarkets) • Vehicle users and beneficiaries (drivers, operators) • Automotive & logistics industry • Industrial associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers in logistics, sustainable mobility, automotive • Logistics and mobility R&D ecosystem • Scientific associated media. • Research & technology associations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public authorities • Government bodies and policy makers • EU associations and initiatives. • Standardisation bodies and technical committees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU citizens, general public and society at large • Civil organisations • Mass media

Figure 1. Shift2Zero target audiences

These four main audiences have been further divided into **8 specific stakeholder target groups**, as outlined during the proposal phase. The project’s Communication, Dissemination, and Clustering strategies include targeted actions to directly engage these groups.

The following table provides an overview of the specific segments within each target group, along with relevant examples.

Table 1. Shift2Zero target groups mapping

STG#	Group	Relevance of Shift2Zero results and its outcomes
1	Mobility fleet managers and LSPs	Availability and access to SotA N1 zero-emission vehicle concepts built upon their needs, collaborating with authorities to accommodate deployment of future urban operations
2	Automotive OEMs	Dialogue with end-users and authorities to increase market acceptance of N1 vehicles, consolidating leadership in market segment. Cooperation across OEMs for knowledge transfer & improved operations thanks to collaborative logistics.
3	Automotive industrial value chain	Enhanced collaboration with multiple OEMs and across value chain, gaining insights on final end-user needs.

² https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-dissemination-and-exploitation_en

4	Logistics chain (retailers, markets)	Improved collaboration with suppliers and optimised operations for clients' satisfaction enabled by active involvement in the process of shaping future urban logistics ecosystem.
5	Vehicle users (drivers, operators)	Enhanced positioning in labour market for upskilling of future logistics vehicles and operations thanks to dedicated training.
6	Public authorities	Adaptive policymaking, increased governance and collaboration frameworks with industry, enhanced decision making with interoperable digital tools leveraging data standards also enabling peer-to-peer collaboration with other authorities.
7	RTOs & academia	Increased knowledge and understanding in eLCVs requirements, design, and deployment with positive urban impact.
8	Citizens	Increased awareness on benefits of eLCVs and impact of logistics deliveries, improved urban ecosystems for healthier lives.

2.2 Channels and key messages

For communication and dissemination activities, the Shift2Zero project will utilise a **diverse range of channels and actions**, including social media campaigns, media relations, promotional materials, scientific publications, workshops, targeted stakeholder engagement events, and presentations at key industry and academic events.

In addition to the official project channels, all partners will leverage their own communication platforms—such as websites, social media presence, and corporate newsletters/publications—to disseminate news about Shift2Zero, ensuring broader reach and greater impact.

Figure 2. Shift2Zero communication and dissemination channels

On the other hand, the communication and dissemination plan messages have been carefully crafted and tailored to each defined target group and will be adapted across the various Shift2Zero communication and dissemination channels. These messages align with the project's core communication, dissemination and clustering objectives, effectively conveying the potential and impact of the research and development carried out.

The following messages will be refined and adapted to ensure they resonate with all audiences—both specialised and non-specialised—making the actions and results of the project accessible and understandable to a broad range of stakeholders.

2.2.1 General, non-specialised key messages

The general messages that Shift2Zero project will address to stakeholders include:

1. Driving zero-emission urban logistics for a greener future mobility

Shift2Zero, funded by the European Commission, shapes the future of urban mobility by developing innovative electric light commercial vehicles (e-LCVs) that help cut emissions and improve efficiency in city logistics.

2. Delivering tailored solutions for real-world needs

The project creates mission-focused e-LCVs designed to meet the diverse demands of urban logistics, ensuring practicality, sustainability, and efficiency.

3. Accelerating the transition to clean transport

By improving existing vehicle platforms and working with industry leaders, Shift2Zero makes zero-emission logistics a reality, supporting cities in their journey toward cleaner and more sustainable mobility.

2.2.2 Key messages tailored per target group

For each TG (see Table 1), Shift2Zero's dissemination and communication efforts will deliver key messages emphasising the project's benefits tailored to their needs. These messages will be updated and refined as needed throughout the project's duration.

STG#1 – Mobility fleet managers and LSPs:

1. Shift2Zero aims to develop efficient and modular e-LCVs that lower operational costs, reduce emissions, and comply with evolving EU regulations for sustainable goals.
2. The project's vehicle solutions will ensure logistics operators to maximise efficiency and reliability in urban deliveries.
3. Shift2Zero upgrades proven platforms to provide fleets with practical, scalable solutions that align with real-world logistics needs.

STG#2 – Automotive OEMs:

1. Shift2Zero pioneers the future of electric light commercial vehicles by integrating optimised energy efficiency and mission-adapted designs.
2. By collaborating with industry leaders, Shift2Zero refines existing vehicle platforms to improve range, durability, and cost-effectiveness.
3. With tailored and scalable solutions, Shift2Zero helps OEMs stay ahead in the shift toward climate-neutral logistics.

STG#3 – Automotive industrial value chain:

1. Shift2Zero fosters collaborations across the supply chain to develop high-performance, cost-effective, and scalable zero-emission vehicle solutions.
2. From advanced battery systems to lightweight materials and modular solutions, Shift2Zero enhances vehicle efficiency and durability.
3. By aligning with sustainability trends, the project enables suppliers to tap into the growing demand for zero-emission urban logistics solutions.

STG#4 – Logistics chain:

1. Shift2Zero enables businesses to transition to clean, efficient urban deliveries with tailored electric vehicle solutions and flexible solutions for efficient transshipment operations.
2. Zero-emission logistics help retailers align with customer expectations for sustainability and corporate responsibility.
3. With mission-adapted e-LCVs, retailers can maintain delivery efficiency while reducing their environmental footprint.

STG#5 – Vehicle users:

1. Shift2Zero develops vehicles with improved comfort, safety, performance, and intuitive technology to support daily operations.
2. Designed for real-world needs, Shift2Zero e-LCVs offer strong range and charging efficiency.
3. The project will support drivers in the transition to clean mobility.

STG#6 – Public authorities:

1. The Shift2Zero project supports clean air policies with zero-emission logistics and helps cities reduce pollution by advancing electric vehicle adoption for urban deliveries.
2. Shift2Zero contributes to climate neutrality goals and urban mobility strategies and new regulations, aligning with EU sustainability targets.
3. Efficient, zero-emission transport solutions improve traffic flow and air quality, benefiting communities and businesses alike.

STG#7 – RTOs & academia:

1. The project fosters collaboration between research institutions and industry to develop cutting-edge e-LCV technologies, advancing research in sustainable mobility solutions.
2. By integrating academic research into vehicle development, Shift2Zero ensures practical, scalable solutions for zero-emission logistics, bridging the gap between innovation and real-world application.

3. The project provides valuable data and case studies that drive policy recommendations and technological advancements contributing to the future of clean transport.

STG#8 – Citizens:

1. Shift2Zero supports cities in reducing emissions from delivery vehicles, leading to healthier air for everyone.
2. Zero-emission transport solutions contribute to quieter, safer, and more environmentally friendly cities, building a sustainable future for urban mobility.
3. By transforming delivery fleets, Shift2Zero makes sustainable urban transport a reality, benefiting both businesses and communities and encouraging green innovation in everyday logistics.

3. Communication, dissemination and clustering management

3.1 Distribution of responsibilities

The Shift2Zero communication, dissemination, and clustering strategy relies on the active participation and commitment of all project partners to effectively showcase the project and its key outcomes.

BAX leads **WP8: Achieving route to market, scalability and replication**, which includes **T8.1: Communication and Dissemination** and **ST8.3.3: Clustering activities and Stakeholder Advisory Board**, both led by EUT.

As task leaders, EUT oversees information exchange within the consortium, coordinate dissemination efforts, establish Shift2Zeros' visual identity and website, develop communication materials, and manage content for the project's social media channels.

Additionally, all consortium members play a crucial role in ensuring the successful implementation of communication, dissemination, and clustering initiatives, helping to maximise outreach and engagement with key stakeholders' groups as defined in the project's objectives.

3.2 Requirements

All communication and dissemination materials produced within the project (presentations, promotional materials, publications, posters, videos, etc.), and distributed whether in physical or electronic format, will display the EU emblem and funding acknowledgement, in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement.

According to the Grant Agreement: *“Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major*

result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate)".

Figure 3. EU funding emblem

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however, give them the right of exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark of logo, either by registration or by any other means.

In addition, all communication or dissemination activities must indicate the following disclaimer, in Table 2:

Table 2. EU funding disclaimer of Shift2Zero

Disclaimer

The Shift2Zero project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Europe Programme: project num. 101192375. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Regarding scientific publications based on the project's research, a specific claim will be used:

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101192375 – Shift2Zero project.

3.3 Ethics, gender and inclusiveness

The Shift2Zero project integrates ethical, societal, and inclusive considerations into its decision-making processes throughout its implementation.

Gender Equality & Inclusivity

Project partners prioritise fairness and equity in visual materials, ensuring they do not reinforce stereotypes in technology or perpetuate historical biases related to gender, ethnicity, or religion. For example, the selection of images for the project website has been carefully curated to reflect these values.

The project also promotes gender sensitivity by crafting inclusive messages and striving for balanced representation in roundtable discussions and speaker panels. The

communication team is trained in gender-sensitive and non-sexist communication practices to uphold these principles.

Integrity & Transparency

Shift2Zero’s communication and dissemination efforts are guided by accuracy, honesty, and reason, while upholding core values such as freedom of expression, diversity of viewpoints, and tolerance. Hate speech and discrimination of any form are strictly rejected across all communication channels.

The project is committed to transparency, recognising its responsibility to both the funding body and taxpayers supporting the research. This commitment is upheld while respecting partner confidentiality, particularly regarding specific technological developments. By adhering to ethical and inclusive standards, Shift2Zero enhances its credibility, strengthens public trust, and fosters engagement from both the funding institution and the broader community.

Ethical Oversight

During project meetings, task leaders and communication participants are encouraged to openly discuss potential ethical concerns, fostering a culture of collective reflection and accountability (D1.3 Data management plan and ethical guidelines give more insight on the ethics practices to be followed).

3.4 Monitoring and reporting

3.4.1 KPIs and activities reporting

EUT has created an Excel file to systematically track all communication and dissemination activities carried out by consortium members throughout the project’s duration. This file is securely stored in the SharePoint online repository, providing easy access for all partners. It records essential information, including the description of each activity, target audience, date and location, involved partners, number of people reached, feedback received, and the relevant Work Package (WP) or Task.

Project: Shift2Zero Doc: Communication & Dissemination Activities Execution timeline: 01/01/2025 - 30/06/2028			
Mandatory	Mandatory	Optional / If applicable	Mandatory
Status activity	Type of action (select from dropdown menu)	Type of publication (just for scientific publications)	Short explanation of the action
Planned / Intended	Conferences	NA	EXAMPLE: Paper titled "xxxxxx" submitted at the conference XXX
Attended / participated / action done	(Website)		Inclusion of Shift2Zero information at EUT's website
Attended / participated / action done	(Website)		Inclusion of Shift2Zero information at IKA's website
Attended / participated / action done	(Website)		Inclusion of Shift2Zero information at VUB's website
Attended / participated / action done	(Website)		Information of Shift2Zero KoM published at ITL's website
Attended / participated / action done	(Website)		Inclusion of Shift2Zero information at IFL's website
Attended / participated / action done	(Website)		Inclusion of Shift2Zero information at LPT's website
Attended / participated / action done	(Website)		Inclusion of Shift2Zero information at VUB's website
Planned / Intended	Exhibition		Showcasing S2Z solutions at Transports Logistics Munich
Attended / participated / action done	(Other)		Inclusion of S2Z in the IDADA's #IRIShighlights newsletter
Attended / participated / action done	(Other)		Inclusion of S2Z in the ALICE's newsletter
In preparation			
Abstract / publication submitted			
Cancelled / not done			
Proposal			
Abstract / publication accepted			
Abstract / publication rejected			

Figure 4. Comm&Diss Excel Tracking

The file is organised in the following columns:

- Status activity, with a breakdown menu including several options to report on depending on the activity type (proposal, planned/intended, in preparation, abstract/publication submitted, abstract/publication accepted, abstract/publication rejected, attended/participated/action done, cancelled not done).
- Type of activity, offering a breakdown menu of multiple activity types:
 - [Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)]
 - [Exhibition]
 - [Flyer]
 - [Rollup]
 - [Poster]
 - [Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]
 - [Organisation of a conference]
 - [Organisation of a workshop]
 - [Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)]
 - [Participation to a conference (POSTER)]
 - [Participation to a conference (TALK)]
 - [Participation to a workshop]
 - [Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop]
 - [Press release]
 - [Social media - LINKEDIN]
 - [Social media - TWITTER]
 - [Trade fair]
 - [Training]
 - [Video/film]
 - [Brokerage event]
 - [Pitch event]
 - [Website]
 - [Scientific publication]
 - [Other]
- Type of publication, just for publications, allowing to select from four options (article in journal, conference/workshop proceedings, books/monographies, chapter in books).
- Short explanation of the action: field to write a description of the action being reported.
- Link to KER / topic disseminated: field to define with KER of the project or topic was disseminated.
- What was disseminated: further explanation on the content disseminated (WP/ Task).
- Date/month
- Place, if applicable (related to events)

- Type of audience, offering a break down menu to select from the stakeholders defined in the EU reporting portal:
 - Scientific community (higher education / research)
 - Industry
 - General public
 - Civil society
 - Media
 - Policy makers
 - Investors
 - Customers
 - Other
- Num. of people of the audience reached
- Secondary type of audience reached (if applicable), allowing to select again from a breakdown menu.
- Num. of people of the audience reached in the secondary audience
- Comments on the audience: open text to describe better the audience reached.
- Partner/s and/or list of authors
- Link / DOI in case of scientific publications
- Comments

Additionally, to monitor KPI achievements monthly, a separate Excel file has been created. EUT will be responsible for updating this file with social media analytics and media coverage data.

KPIs Shift2Zero Digital Channels	Mar-25	Apr-25	May-25	01/0+/2025	Jul-25	Aug-25	Sep-25	Oct-25	Nov-25	Dec-25	Jan-26	Feb-26	Mar-26	Mar-26
	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	
#Likes/reactions	0													
#Impressions	0													
#Shares	0													
YouTube Corporate Account														
# Subscribers														
# New Subscribers														
# Total Videos														
# New Videos														
# Comments														
# Likes														
MailChimp														
# Subscribers														
Twitter Accounts Partners														
# Tweets	0													
# Likes	0													
# Retweets	0													
LinkedIn - Partners Accounts														
# Posts	1													
# Likes	41													
# Comments	2													
# Shares	0													
Facebook / Instagram Partners Accounts														
# Posts	0													
# Likes	0													
# Comments	0													
# Shares	0													

Figure 5. View of Comm&Diss KPIs reporting Excel file

3.4.2 Communication and dissemination KPIs

To evaluate the effectiveness and impact of communication and dissemination efforts, specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been assigned to various project activities. EUT has developed an Excel file to track all communication and dissemination activities, as well as monitor these KPIs throughout the project and assess them at the end. Progress will be documented in project review reports and discussed in project meetings.

This file is stored in the SharePoint online repository, accessible to all partners. It includes details such as the activity description, target audience, date and location, partners involved, number of people reached, feedback received, and information about the related WP/Task.

This monitoring approach will track the project's progress toward its objectives and allow for continuous improvements in the communication and dissemination strategy throughout the project's implementation. By analysing each KPI, challenges and success factors will be identified, enabling the optimization of the strategy and creating a dynamic cycle of planning, execution, evaluation, and adjustment.

Table 3. Communication & Dissemination KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target M42
Website	Number of visits	Website analytics	≥4,000
	Number of page views		≥6,000
	Number of users		≥2,000
Social media	Number of followers in project social media (LinkedIn)	Social Media analytics	≥500
	Publications in partners social media		≥50
Media relations	Number of press releases	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	≥4
	Number of publications in specialized magazines		≥5
	Number of publications in general outlets across Europe		≥25
	Number of citizens reached by media publications		>30.000
	Number of divulgative posts on Shift2Zero website		≥15
Events	Number of events participate (both industrial and academia / scientific events)	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	≥25
	Number of events for non-specialist publics attended		≥2
	Shift2Zero final event		1
Publications	Number of OA peer-reviewed articles	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	5
Clustering activities	Number of cooperation agreement with EU initiatives/projects	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	≥10
	Number of activities with industrial associations across Europe		≥10
Promotional materials	Number of factsheets on each pilot activities	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	≥5
	Number of rollups		1
	Number of trifolds		1

	Number of factsheet (versions for academia and for industry)		1
	General presentation		1
	Audio-visual materials		5
Stakeholder engagement	Number of members in the community of interest	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	≥300
	Number of newsletters		≥6
	Contributions to relevant newsletters		≥2
Stakeholder Advisory Board (AB)	Number of workshops to gather AB feedback	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	2
Training and knowledge transfer	Inclusion of Shift2Zero results in existing training courses	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	3
	Number of webinars on WP3-7 technical results		4
	Site visits to Shift2Zero pilot scenarios		5

3.4.3 Risks and mitigation measures

This section outlines the initial risks associated with communication, dissemination, and clustering, along with contingency plans to mitigate potential challenges and ensure smooth project execution. The full project risk management guidelines and procedures are comprised in D1.2.

To assess the level of exposure to each risk, the project employs a risk matrix, as illustrated in *Figure 6*. This matrix helps evaluate risks systematically and determine appropriate response strategies throughout the project's progression.

	Probability	1- Extremely unlikely	2- Likely	3- Extremely likely
Impact				
1- Not critical		1	2	3
2- Significant		2	4	6
3- Fundamental to continuing operations		3	6	9

Risk score = Impact x Probability Priority: ■ High ■ Medium ■ Low

Figure 6. Risk management matrix

The risks associate with activities outlined in T8.1 and ST8.3.3 and the potential mitigation measures have been identified and exposed in *Table 4*. This table will undergo periodic reviews to identify any emerging risks and assess whether additional mitigation actions need to be implemented.

Table 4. Comm&Diss risks and mitigation measures

Risks	Status	Probability	Impact	Risk score	Mitigation measures
Low participation in dissemination activities (low stakeholder engagement in webinars, workshops and local sessions)	Identified during proposal preparation	2	2	4 Medium	Causes will be assessed, and the dissemination strategy will be revised. Intensive communication campaigns will be launched at least one month in advance to promote project events through relevant channels. Project partners engaged in relevant EU initiatives will act as ambassadors for Shift2Zero, enhancing project dissemination and stakeholder engagement.
The audience has difficulty to understand Shift2Zero solutions	Identified during proposal preparation	2	2	4 Medium	Use real-life examples and simple language while adapting both the technology and messaging to different contexts and audience needs.
Not enough engagement on Shift2Zero communication channels	Identified during proposal preparation	1	2	2 Low	Creation of more content for the project website and social media that engages stakeholders, increase the frequency of publication on project channels. Provision and collection of free-to-use pictures, videos and data for social media actions in Shift2Zero - SharePoint folder.
Low project visibility	New risk – January 2025	1	2	2 Low	Create an engaging website and compelling communication materials. Collaborate on joint activities with other initiatives and projects. Regularly review publication efforts, including trade fair and conference participation, publications, and social media activity, to ensure maximum visibility. Boost efforts in producing audio/visual content for broader use on web platforms like YouTube. Implement search engine optimization (SEO) strategies to improve the website's visibility and increase traffic.

4. Communication tools

4.1 Project branding and templates

As outlined in the work plan, EUT is responsible for designing **Shift2Zero official visual Corporate Identity (VCI)**. Defining the branding of the project is crucial for establishing and strengthening Shift2Zero's identity, ensuring consistency and coherence. Proper use of the established elements and strict adherence to authorised document templates is essential to effectively communicate the project's advancements and goals as a unified brand.

The sections hereinafter outline the key branding elements, including the project's logo, corporate colours palette, fonts, templates, and graphic components. These elements are to be used and implemented across all communication and dissemination activities by all the partners involved in the Shift2Zero project.

4.1.1 Shift2Zero logo

The logo is the main brand element of the Shift2Zero's visual identity, and it represents the core concepts of the project: logistics, mobility, sustainability and zero-emission.

The primary colour palette of the logo combines green and blue tones. While the green colour symbolises environmental awareness and sustainability, blue colours evoke a sense of movement and innovation, which aligns with the project's focus on advancing mobility solutions. The overall design of the logo with these colours combinations highlights the project's vision of achieving a zero-emission urban logistics future.

Figure 7. Shift2Zero full colour logo

Various versions of the logo have been developed, including a full-colour version, positive and negative black-and-white variants (for use when colour application is not possible), and a version for use against the main project background colour.

Figure 8. Inverted colour logo

Figure 9. Inverted black & White logo (left) and Black & White logo (right)

Figure 10. Examples of different uses of the logo

Figure 11. Social media tailored logo

4.1.2 Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) Manual

The VCI manual established the standards for Shift2Zero’s visual identity, outlining the correct use of key elements such as logos, colours, fonts, and promotional materials layouts. This guide has been developed and shared among partners to ensure the integrity and consistency of the project’s branding.

All consortium members should consider this guide as the primary reference for branding materials and design principles, ensuring a unified and professional representation of Shift2Zero across all project-related communications.

The following sections describe some parts included in the manual.

4.1.2.1 Corporate colours

This section presents the **Shift2Zero main colours palette** that must be used in all project materials, such as the website, social media channels and other promotional or graphic elements.

As per the designed palette, the key colours for the project are Green (Pantone: #8ddc6a) and Blue (Pantone: #00a7c0). Both colours are also used and combined to create the Shift2Zero gradient. Additionally, a blue turquoise (Pantone: #0a7d99) and a dark blue (Pantone: #001a4c), complete the palette.

Figure 12. Shift2Zero colours palette

4.1.2.2 Fonts

Two different fonts have been established for use in internal and external documents, as well as promotional materials. **Bai Jamjuree** is the preferred typeface for project’s channels and external promotional content.

On the other hand, **Arial** is the main font for deliverables and internal documents as it is a standard Microsoft Office font included in Word and PowerPoint applications, among others.

Figure 13. Shift2Zero selected font for promotional materials and external documents

4.1.2.3 Other graphic resources

The Shift2Zero VCI manual details different graphic resources to be used during the development of the project’s materials (mainly icons and images).

IMAGES

ICONS

Figure 14. Main graphic resources for the project

4.1.3 Project templates

Various document templates have been created and distributed to all Shift2Zero project partners, including a PowerPoint template (for both internal and external presentations), and four Word templates designed for deliverables, meeting agendas, correspondence, and meeting minutes.

The main purpose of these templates is to ensure a consistent and professional visual identity across all project documentations and communications. By providing a consistent format, they enhance clarity, reinforce the Shift2Zero brand, and facilitate collaboration among partners.

4.1.3.1 Power point template

A customised PowerPoint template has been developed for internal and external presentations throughout the Shift2Zero project.

This template includes a range of slide layouts, allowing users to seamlessly integrate text and visual elements. All partners are encouraged to use and adapt these slides to maintain a consistent and professional presentation style for project-related communications. A preview of sample slides is shown in the figure below.

Figure 15. View of Shift2Zero presentation template

4.1.3.2 Deliverable template

A Word document template has been created and shared with partners to be used for all project's deliverables.

This template details the use of a page header with both the Shift2Zero's logo and the EU funding body's logo. Moreover, a footer including the page number, some information about the document and a distinctive element specifically designed for project's materials.

The document also includes a cover with the details of the document (name of the deliverable, WP / Task related, sensitivity status, deliverable leader, date, etc.) followed by a table summarising the deliverable authors and different versions, the executive summary and a table of contents, figures and tables.

Figure 16. View of the first pages of the deliverable template

The deliverable template is structured with predefined headings for each section, ensuring a clear and consistent format. It specifies the style guidelines for various elements such as tables, figures, and text, while also standardizing the formatting of references and annexes.

Figure 17. View of deliverable template pages

4.1.3.3 Agenda and meeting minutes templates

The template designed for the agenda presents a standardised format, including a header with both the Shift2Zero and funding body logos. This document ensures a consistent and professional appearance for all project agendas.

On the other hand, a template has been designed for documenting meeting discussions and attendance, this template is intended for internal project's meetings. It includes a header page with the Shift2Zero logo and is organised into multiple sections: general meeting details, list of attendees, tables to track updated on each Work Package and Tasks, and a last section for recording action points.

4.1.3.4 Letter template

This document template is specifically designed for correspondence drafted by consortium partners during the Shift2Zero project. It features predefined sections for the sender's details and relevant references to the project.

Figure 20. Shift2Zero letter template

4.2 Project website

At M3, EUT, responsible for communication and dissemination, designed and launched the official Shift2Zero project website under the registered domain www.shift2zero-project.eu.

The website, serving as the anchor for all communication and dissemination activities, has been created to engage all target audiences. It provides access to key public materials, including essential project's information, main objectives, and expected results and impacts. The website will be regularly updated with news, links to other relevant sources, details of scientific publications, conferences and congresses attended, and other relevant content about the project. With the objective to maximise the impact and exploitation of Shift2Zero results the website will remain active at least during three years after the project's finalisation. Additionally, aligned with Shift2Zero's VCI, the website offers direct access to the project's social media profiles.

Considering that different authors might updated the site, a Content Management System (CMS) has been implemented. EUT has recommended WordPress, leveraging its Research Communications Office's (RCO) extensive experience with this platform.

English is the primary language of the website; however, a multilingual plugin will be integrated if translation needs arise. To ensure accessibility across various devices, the website follows a responsive design approach, optimizing performance for smooth browsing on tablets and smartphones.

4.2.1 Website structure

Figure 21 illustrates the structure of the Shift2Zero website. Sections highlighted in blue represent the pages that have already been implemented, while those in green indicate content that will be created later, in alignment with project’s advancements.

Future changes and adjustments to the website structure may be executed to allocate new documents and dissemination actions, as well as to support specific WP or tasks.

Figure 21. Shift2Zero website launch structure

4.2.2 Content of the website

The following sections describe the contents that have been published at the time of the website release.

4.2.2.1 Homepage

The Home is the initial page of the website, and it includes the main information of Shift2Zero. At the beginning it shows a slider with text and a button to “About Shift2Zero” section, and different blocks introducing the project. Additionally, a section mentioning the consortium and linking to the partners page will be designed and included in the homepage. On the other hand, a section showing the latest publications of the “News & Events” page will be created and published through the homepage.

HOME SLIDER

ACCELERATING ZERO-EMISSION URBAN LOGISTICS

Innovative e-LCVs designs for emission-free logistics and sustainable mobility

[Button: **About Shift2Zero**]

SHIFT2ZERO IN A NUTSHELL

Advancing zero-emission logistics solutions for sustainable urban mobility

In urban areas across Europe, achieving zero-emission logistics is no longer just a policy preference, but a growing and crucial necessity.

Shift2Zero is a European project pioneering innovative designs and cutting-edge solutions for zero-emission electric light commercial vehicles (e-LCVS), tailored to meet the evolving needs of urban logistics.

The project's primary goal is to reduce road transport emissions and to enhance operational efficiency, ensuring that the solutions developed are aligned with real-world challenges.

[Button: **Find out more**]

PILLARS

Shift2Zero features

- ✓ **Significant CO₂ reduction:** optimised vehicle design and energy-efficient systems to lower emissions.
- ✓ **Increased adoption of e-LCVs:** overcoming cost and operational barriers for wider electric light commercial vehicle use.
- ✓ **Enhanced safety for drivers & pedestrians:** sustainable materials and additive manufacturing to improve N1 vehicle safety.
- ✓ **Future-proof logistics:** adaptable, scalable vehicle solutions to ensure long-term operational efficiency.

ALIGNED WITH EUROPEAN NEEDS

Solving the challenges of urban logistics and climate goals

According to the World Economic Forum, vehicle activity is expected to rise by 36% by 2030, potentially leading to a 32% increase in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions if existing practices persist.

Current market dynamics reveal a gap between existing N1 vehicles supply and the evolving demands of urban logistics and climate goals, creating a clear need for innovative and sustainable automotive solutions.

Shift2Zero is designed to address these challenges by leveraging the advantages of both N1 vehicle platforms and purpose-built designs, driving the transition to zero-emission logistics.

- ✓ **Smarter urban logistics:** zero-emission solutions optimised for growing sectors like e-commerce, groceries, and cold chain logistics.
- ✓ **Safer and more affordable vehicles:** mission-specific, user-centred electric light commercial vehicles (e-LCVs).
- ✓ **Collaboration with the industry:** engagement with logistics companies, fleet operators, and freight users to align innovations with real market needs.
- ✓ **Accelerating green transition:** support the EU's vision of reducing GHG emissions by 55% by 2030 and achieving climate neutrality by 2050.

QUOTE

“By engaging leading European industrial transport experts at the component, vehicle and system levels, Shift2Zero aims to strengthen the EU's position as a global leader in the transport market, with a particular focus on the e-LCV segment.” Fanny Breuil, Project Coordinator – Eurecat Technology Centre

OUR INNOVATIONS

Validating Shift2Zero vehicle concepts in real-life operations

Shift2Zero performs four pilots and one macro-pilot to demonstrate its six new vehicle concepts in scalable zero-emission real-world scenarios.

The project will develop and validate six innovative e-LCVs concepts to enhance operational efficiency and user comfort.

These concepts will be equipped with advanced sensors and software to optimise routes, reduce energy consumption and maximise fleet efficiency. By integrating synchromodal and logistics innovations, Shift2Zero ensures that transport is not only efficient but also connected to the next generations of logistics systems.

- Optimised thermal comfort
- Modular swappable concept
- Geofenced N1 vehicles for safe & sustainable driving in urban areas
- Holistic smart energy management
- Multi-temperature cargo body
- Optimised space for dual transport

[Button: **More about our pilots**]

STAY IN TOUCH!

Be part of our community of interest!

Keep updated on the project progress and be the first to know about our latest results while you connect with other experts and citizens interested in urban logistics solutions.

[Button: **Subscribe now!**]

NEWS & EVENTS

Project news

[a carousel of the latest news]

PARTNERS

Meet our team

Shift2Zero interdisciplinary consortium is made up of 30 partners from 10 European countries working together for the development of zero-emission electric vehicles for urban logistics.

The project is coordinated by Eurecat Technology Centre.

[Button: **About Shift2Zero consortium**]

Accelerating zero-emission urban logistics

Innovative e-LCVs designs for emission-free logistics and sustainable mobility

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

SHIFT2ZERO IN A NUTSHELL

Advancing zero-emission logistics solutions for sustainable urban mobility

In urban areas across Europe, **achieving zero-emission logistics** is no longer just a policy preference, but a growing and crucial necessity.

Shift2Zero is a European project pioneering **innovative designs and cutting-edge solutions for zero-emission electric light commercial vehicles (e-LCVs)**, tailored to meet the evolving needs of urban logistics.

The project's primary goal is to **reduce road transport emissions and to enhance operational efficiency**, ensuring that the solutions developed are aligned with real-world challenges.

[+ FIND OUT MORE](#)

PILLARS

Shift2Zero features

Significant CO₂ reduction

Optimized vehicle design and energy-efficient systems to lower emissions.

Increased adoption of e-LCVs

Overcoming cost and operational barriers for wider electric light commercial vehicle use.

Enhanced safety for drivers & pedestrians

Sustainable materials and additive manufacturing to improve N1 vehicle safety.

Future-proof logistics

Adaptable, scalable vehicle solutions to ensure long-term operational efficiency.

ALIGNED WITH EUROPEAN NEEDS

Solving the challenges of urban logistics and climate goals

According to the [World Economic Forum](#), vehicle activity is expected to rise by 36% by 2030, potentially **leading to a 32% increase in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions** if existing practices persist.

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- ▾ Smarter urban logistics
- ▾ Safer and more affordable vehicles
- ▾ Collaboration with the industry
- ▾ Accelerating green transition

“By engaging leading European industrial transport experts at the component, vehicle and system levels, Shift2zero aims to strengthen the EU’s position as a global leader in the transport market, with a particular focus on the e-LCV segment.

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- ➔ Optimised thermal comfort
- ➔ Modular swappable concept
- ➔ Geofenced N1 vehicles for safe & sustainable driving in urban areas
- ➔ Holistic smart energy management
- ➔ Multi-temperature cargo body
- ➔ Optimised space for dual transport

[MORE ABOUT OUR PILOTS](#)

Stay in touch

Be part of our community of interest!

Keep updated on the project progress and be the first to know about our latest results while you connect with other experts and citizens interested in urban logistics solutions.

[SUBSCRIBE NOW!](#)

NEWS & EVENTS

Follow our journey!

PROJECT NEWS

Shift2Zero delivered messages to EGUM Subgroup “City Access for Business”

April 8, 2025

The Shift2Zero project jointly organised an online workshop “City Access for Business – Zero Emission Freight Vehicles in Cities”, with Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (ALICE).

[Read more](#)

Shift2Zero project kicks off to drive zero-emission logistics

January 2, 2025

The Shift2Zero project kick-off meeting was held in Barcelona with the objective of advancing zero-emission logistics solutions for sustainable urban mobility

[Read more](#)

SHIFT2ZERO AGENDA

Upcoming events

-
Webinar: City Access for Business: Zero Emission Freight Vehicles in Cities
 7 April 2025 | Presenting Shift2Zero in this webinar with key stakeholders discussing on the implementation of EU Urban Mobility Framework.
-
Transport Logistic Munich 2025
 2 - 5 June 2025 | Shift2Zero will be represented during the Transport Logistic Munich fair.
-
Shift2Zero General Assembly
 17 - 19 September 2025 | Celebration of the first Shift2Zero General Assembly in Bergen (Norway)

[Check upcoming events](#)

PARTNERS

Meet our team

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[ABOUT SHIFT2ZERO CONSORTIUM](#)

5

RTOs

4

Academia institutions

15

Industries & SMEs

5

Public administrations

1

Logistics Innovation entity

Figure 22. View of Shift2Zero’s homepage

4.2.2.2 About Shift2Zero

This page includes more detailed information about the project including its objectives, phases, expected impacts, the pilots and the solutions to be developed:

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Shifting to zero-emission logistics with right-sized, mission-focused, N1 eLCVs

As urban logistics evolve, the demand for zero-emission solutions is more urgent than ever. However, the transition to electric light commercial vehicles (eLCVs) in the European Union remains slow due to a lack of efficient designs tailored for diverse

logistics needs. This highlights the urgent need for purpose-built eLCVs to progress towards the EU's sustainable logistics and climate neutrality goals.

Shift2Zero addresses these challenges by developing innovative and mission-focused N1 e-LCVs designs and functionalities that enhance efficiency, reduce emissions, and align with evolving logistics requirements.

To do that, two proven platforms – IVECO's e-Daily (heavier N1 segment) and Alkè's ATX (lighter, custom-build LCV segment) – are being upgraded during the project for their potential to offer a right-fitted solution to logistics operators. These platforms have already proven their performance and fit for transport operations within various applications. These platforms will be fitted with Michelin's tire.

The Shift2Zero's solutions are to better meet logistics and end-users demands while accelerating the adoption of zero-emission transport solutions and more sustainable future mobility.

WHAT WE DO

Developing six novel vehicle concepts

With these solutions, Shift2Zero aims to address both the supply (operational and industrial requirements) and the shifting demand (increased e-commerce and fresh product delivery).

- **Multi-temperature controlled, optimised and energy-efficient cargo body:** Efficient eutectic evaporators and airflow integration allow mixed transport of fresh, temperature-sensitive, and dry goods, reducing fleet size and emissions.
- **Optimised thermal comfort and safe ergonomics in vehicles' cabin:** Advancing vehicle safety through sustainable design, including pedestrian protection and passive safety improvements. The approach also significantly reduces manufacturing lead time, weight and achieves substantial cost reduction.
- **Holistic energy management for cold chain logistics:** Combining regenerative braking, advanced tire technology, and bi-directional charging for greater efficiency and sustainability.
- **Modular swappable transshipment units:** Standardised cargo modules improve operational flexibility, reducing handling and boosting efficiency.
- **Geofenced N1 vehicles for urban safety:** Implementing open-standard logistics solutions for geofencing, curbside reservations, and pedestrian-friendly design.
- **Dual-use modular vehicles for goods and passenger transport:** Flexible seating and IoT-powered safety measures enable efficient transport of both people and cargo.

PROJECT PHASES

Proposing a user-centred design approach

One of Shift2Zero's strengths is placing end-users at the core of its innovation process. By involving logistics operators, fleet managers, policy makers, and industry

stakeholders from the start, the project ensures that its new vehicle concepts meet current and future supply and demand needs for the commercial delivery of goods.

1. Identification of user needs & demands
2. Translation of insights into technical requirements
3. Deployment & testing novel vehicle concepts in real-life operations
4. Enhancing adoption rates

OUR VISION

Shift2Zero innovations are stemming directly from end-user engagement and are therefore anticipated to foster rapid acceptance. By reducing particle emissions with advanced tire technology and better brake systems, the project aims to improve air quality and make these solutions more appealing.

EXPECTED IMPACTS

Driving sustainable logistics forward

- ✓ **Significant CO2 reduction:** through optimised vehicle design and energy-efficient systems, including tires and brakes.
- ✓ **Increased adoption of e-LCVs:** by addressing cost and operational barriers.
- ✓ **Enhanced driver safety and pedestrian protection:** for N1 vehicles through sustainable materials and additive manufacturing.
- ✓ **Future-proofing logistics operations:** with adaptable, scalable vehicle solutions.

STAY IN TOUCH!

Interested? Keep up to date on Shift2Zero project's developments by subscribing to our newsletter.

[Button: **Subscribe now!**]

OUR PILOTS

Five pilots in six European cities

Shift2Zero develops four pilots and one macro-pilot to demonstrate its six new vehicle concepts in scalable zero-emission real-life operations.

- Bergen (Norway)
- Oslo (Norway)
- Thessaloniki (Greece)
- Bologna (Italy)
- Brussels (Belgium)
- Wroclaw (Poland)

[Button: **Find out more**]

About Shift2Zero

SHIFT2ZERO PROJECT

Shifting to zero-emission logistics with right-sized, mission-focused, N1 eLCVs

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The Shift2Zero's solutions are to better meet logistics and end-users demands while **accelerating the adoption of zero-emission transport solutions and more sustainable future mobility.**

Execution period

1st January 2025 -
30th June 2028

Budget

€12M (€10M EU
contribution)

Funding program

Horizon Europe, CL5-
2024-D5-01-06

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With these solutions, Shift2Zero aims to **address both the supply** (operational and industrial requirements) **and the shifting demand** (increased e-commerce and fresh product delivery).

<p>Multi-temperature controlled, optimised and energy-efficient cargo body</p> <p>Efficient eutectic evaporators and airflow integration allow mixed transport of fresh, temperature-sensitive, and dry goods, reducing fleet size and emissions.</p>	<p>Optimised thermal comfort and safe ergonomics in vehicles' cabin</p> <p>Advancing vehicle safety through sustainable design, including pedestrian protection and passive safety improvements. The approach also significantly reduces manufacturing lead time, weight and achieves substantial cost reduction.</p>	<p>Holistic energy management for cold chain logistics</p> <p>Combining regenerative braking, advanced tire technology, and bi-directional charging for greater efficiency and sustainability.</p>
<p>Modular swappable transshipment units</p> <p>Standardised cargo modules improve operational flexibility, reducing handling and boosting efficiency.</p>	<p>Geofenced N1 vehicles for urban safety</p> <p>Implementing open-standard logistics solutions for geofencing, curbside reservations, and pedestrian-friendly design.</p>	<p>Dual-use modular vehicles for goods and passenger transport</p> <p>Flexible seating and IoT-powered safety measures enable efficient transport of both people and cargo.</p>

PROJECT PHASES

Proposing a user-centred design approach

One of Shift2Zero's strengths is placing end-users at the core of its innovation process. By involving logistics operators, fleet managers, policy makers, and industry stakeholders from the start, the project ensures that its new vehicle concepts meet current and future supply and demand needs for the commercial delivery of goods.

“ OUR VISION

Shift2Zero innovations are stemming directly from end-user engagement and are therefore anticipated to foster rapid acceptance. By reducing particle emissions with advanced tire technology and better brake systems, the project aims to improve air quality and make these solutions more appealing.

EXPECTED IMPACTS

Driving sustainable logistics forward

- ✓ Significant CO₂ reduction
through optimised vehicle design and energy-efficient systems, including tires and brakes
- ✓ Increased adoption of e-LCVs
by addressing cost and operational barriers
- ✓ Enhanced driver safety and pedestrian protection
for N1 Vehicles through sustainable materials and additive manufacturing
- ✓ Future-proofing logistics operations
with adaptable, scalable vehicle solutions

INTERESTED?

**Keep up to date on Shift2Zero project's developments by
subscribing to our newsletter**

[SUBSCRIBE NOW!](#)

OUR PILOTS

Five pilots in six European cities

Shift2Zero develops four pilots and one macro-pilot to demonstrate its six new vehicle concepts in scalable zero-emission real-life operations.

- Bergen (Norway)
- Oslo (Norway)
- Thessaloniki (Greece)
- Bologna (Italy)
- Brussels (Belgium)
- Wroclaw (Poland)

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

Figure 23. View of "About Shift2Zero" page

4.2.2.3 Consortium

This section highlights the corporate information of project partners. It starts with an overview of the consortium, followed by a portfolio featuring the logos of all participating organisations. Each logo links to a dedicated page with detailed information about the partner, including their contact details.

MEET THE TEAM

A collaborative European consortium to zero-emission urban logistics

A user-centric vehicle innovation requires an interdisciplinary approach. Shift2Zero brings together a multidisciplinary consortium involving partners representing from across the entire supply chain of logistics vehicles and operations to drive the transition toward zero-emission urban logistics.

This Horizon Europe project, coordinated by Eurecat Technology Centre, brings together 30 partners (29 partners and 1 affiliated entity) coming from 10 European countries (Spain, Belgium, Austria, Italy, Norway, Greece, Germany, Poland, France and Czech Republic).

**Following the example below, all partners information has been included on the website.*

Eurecat – Coordinator

eurecat Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The centre offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 750 professionals who generate a volume of income of 60M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value and has over 200 patents.

Contribution to Shift2Zero

Eurecat is in charge of the project management through the Unit of Product Innovation and Multiphysics Simulation Unit. With a solid experience participating and coordinating international research projects in this field, EUT will be the lead partner in the development of innovations to be included in the vehicles that will circulate in the pilots. The Eurecat's Audiovisual Technologies Unit will collaborate in immersive visualisation using Virtual or extended Reality, while its Training Department will deploy a specialised training program for logistics end-users and workers. Additionally, EUT will manage the Communication and Dissemination activities through its Research's Communication Office.

www.eurecat.org

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/>

Instagram: [@eurecat_org](https://www.instagram.com/eurecat_org)

Twitter: [@Eurecat_News](https://twitter.com/Eurecat_News)

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWeVIFJ_t_6ozc7bDaKZw

Partners

MEET THE TEAM

A collaborative European consortium to zero-emission urban logistics

30

Partners

10

EU countries

A user-centric vehicle innovation requires an interdisciplinary approach. **Shift2Zero** brings together a multidisciplinary consortium involving partners representing from across the entire supply chain of logistics vehicles and operations to drive the transition toward zero-emission urban logistics.

This Horizon Europe project, coordinated by **Eurecat Technology Centre**, brings together **30 partners** (29 partners and 1 affiliated entity) coming from **10 European countries** (Spain, Belgium, Austria, Italy, Norway, Greece, Germany, Poland, France and Czech Republic).

OUR PARTNERS

TØI- Institute of Transport Economics

Bax Innovation

ALICE

Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH)

Applus IDIADA

Michelin

IVECO

Łukasiewicz Automotive Industry Institute

Łukasiewicz – Poznań Institute of Technology

Alkè Electric Vehicles

Municipality of Bologna

Wrocław Municipality

Figure 24. View of part of "Consortium" page

4.2.2.4 Pilots

This page provides comprehensive information about Shift2Zero's pilots and offers access to in-depth details for each one.

SHIFT2ZERO INNOVATIONS VALIDATION

Vehicle concepts piloted in five real-life scenarios

Shift2Zero develops four pilots and one macro-pilot to demonstrate its six new vehicle concepts in scalable zero-emission real-life operations.

The pilots, conducted over six different European cities from five countries, are representative of diverse urban realities of North, West, Central and Southern Europe. This allows extensive good practice and knowledge sharing while keeping context-specific replicability of solutions.

Each pilot tests the vehicle concepts in different combinations, exploring potential synergies to meet diversifying current and future user requirements.

6 European cities | 5 European countries | 5 end-users

THE PILOTS

- Modularity, standardisation and access regulations: Norwegian macro-pilot (Bergen and Oslo)
- Logistics as a service, business model diversification: Brussels (Belgium) pilot
- Transshipment Thessaloniki: Thessaloniki (Greece) pilot
- Transshipment Bologna: Bologna (Italy) pilot
- Synchromodality: Wroclaw (Poland) pilot

Pilots

SHIFT2ZERO INNOVATIONS VALIDATION

Vehicle concepts piloted in five real-life scenarios

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6 European cities

5 European countries

5 end-users

The pilots

Modularity, standardisation and access regulations
Norwegian macro-pilot (Bergen and Oslo)
[+ MORE INFORMATION](#)

Logistics as a service, business model diversification
Brussels (Belgium) pilot
[+ MORE INFORMATION](#)

Transshipment Thessaloniki
Thessaloniki (Greece) pilot
[+ MORE INFORMATION](#)

Transshipment Bologna
Bologna (Italy) pilot
[+ MORE INFORMATION](#)

Synchromodality
Wroclaw (Poland) pilot
[+ MORE INFORMATION](#)

Figure 25. View of "Pilots" page

Norwegian macro-pilot

NORWEGIAN MACRO-PILOT

Modularity, standardisation and access regulations

In this macro-pilot, partners from DHL Express will be **testing the modular swappable concept for seamless standardised transshipments** to reduce refill times across different types of vehicles. This will create flexibility to distribute and exchange swap boxes with vehicles already on route.

In Bergen, DHL Express will collaborate with the City of Bergen to explore geofenced right-sized vehicles for safe driving in restricted urban areas, testing data specifications in combination with logistics vehicles.

This pilot will **reveal the e-LCVs movements and allow for more streamlined interaction with available infrastructure and other road users.**

“

DHL Express could extend the modular swappable box concept across its operations, both in Norway (8 locations) and in Europe (28 countries). The use of integrated data specifications for dynamic urban space management can be compared and transferred across the 6 European cities of Shift2Zero pilots, as well as within other European cities.

PILOT LEADERS

CITY OF
BERGEN

Figure 26. Example of a page dedicated to specific pilots

4.2.2.5 News & Events

This section showcases articles on Shift2Zero project advancements, key results, and general assembly meetings, along with partner contributions on project-related topics.

It also features an agenda of upcoming events where the Shift2Zero consortium is organising or participating, including conferences, meetings, exhibitions, congresses, and workshops. Additionally, a catalogue of past events is available, detailing dissemination activities.

Project-hosted events—such as the final conference, webinars, and workshops—will be announced and promoted here. Each event will have a dedicated page with key details, the agenda, and a registration form. Afterward, materials like presentations, documents, and video recordings will be available for download.

Figure 27. View of “News & Events” section

4.2.2.6 Results

A “Results” page will be created to gather all public materials of the project, including visual materials, videos, public deliverables, scientific publications, and media features. Specific pages for each type of content will be created depending on the number of results for a correct visualisation.

Main outcomes:

- **Deliverables:** all public reports will be published on this website for in-depth access to project outputs.
- **Promotional materials:** project promotional materials produced (rollups, infosheets, posters, etc).
- **Scientific publications:** all scientific articles related to the project’s research in open access journals or as conference proceedings.
- **Audiovisual materials:** a set of short videos will be produced to present S2Z’s concept and impacts.
- **Media impacts:** main articles featuring S2Z project in generalist and specialised media outlets.

4.2.2.7 Contact

This section includes a contact form where visitors can submit comments and inquiries. The form features fields for Name, Company, Email, Subject, and Message, ensuring structured communication.

As an alternative contact method, the dedicated email address info@shift2zero-project.eu is displayed on the website. Managed by the project coordinator, this email account ensures efficient handling of information requests.

Figure 28. View of “Contact” section

4.2.3 Layout

The Shift2Zero website menu is accessible from all pages, allowing visitors to navigate seamlessly and find the information they need, regardless of their entry point.

The website’s overall design and homepage incorporate the following elements:

Header

- Shift2Zero logo to appear in the header.
- Navigation menu.
- Search button.
- Access to Social Media platforms (LinkedIn, YouTube).

Footer

- EU logo to appear in the footer. Under the logo will appear the phrase "The Shift2Zero project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Europe Programme: project num. 101192375. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them"
- Link to legal notice.
- Link to privacy statement.
- Link to cookies policy.
- Link to newsletter subscription
- Contact info and access to social media platforms.

Figure 29. Header and footer layout

Home About Shift2Zero Consortium Pilots News & Events Contact

Figure 30. Shift2Zero website header

Figure 31. Shift2Zero website footer

4.2.4 Managing and updating policy

The website has been designed and developed by EUT with input from all consortium partners. The Shift2Zero website will be regularly updated with new content and information whenever a dissemination action takes place, a result is achieved, or there is news worth sharing.

4.2.5 Analytics

The Shift2Zero website uses Matomo in the platform's backend to monitor traffic and generate periodic performance reports. Unlike Google Analytics, Matomo prioritises data security and privacy, ensuring full data ownership and preventing any data from being shared with third parties.

Figure 32. View of Matomo website analytics panel

Since its launch in M3 (beginning of April 2025), the website has received **311 visits, 812 page views, 217 users and 2.9 actions per visit**, including page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches per visit (*Data Analytics from 29th April 2025*).

4.2.6 Site, hosting, installation and management

EUT has been responsible for setting up the website, including domain purchase, hosting, and WordPress.org configuration, as well as creating content and designing the fixed sections. EUT, on the other hand, is responsible for maintaining the site until the project's completion, regularly adding and updating content. All pages have been optimised for search engines (SEO) to ensure strong visibility in search results. The website will remain active and maintained for four years after the project's completion.

4.2.7 Data protection

The Shift2Zero website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR.

The website has been adapted to the latest directives published by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) on July 2020, which came into force on October 31st, 2020 with the purpose to align the cookies installation with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) consent requirements. The latest version of the AEPD “Guidelines on the Use of Cookies”, compared with the previous one, specifies that the consent must be granted by clearly accepting the cookies or carrying out similar actions to click “I accept”. In that sense, browsing the website or the use the scroll bar cannot be construed as an affirmative action, nor the use of cookie walls that do not provide an alternative to the consent.

In order to comply with the new AEPD directives, EUT, as the owner of the website www.shift2zero-project.eu, has installed a cookies banner allowing the user to decide on which non-necessary cookies to install. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics will only be tracked for users accepting this type of cookies, which may result in losing some statistics on the number of web visits, page viewed or number of users.

The users may revise their cookies’ selection at any time as the Cookies Setting Banner is available at the bottom right part of the page. The website also includes specific pages for allocating the privacy policy (<https://shift2zero-project.eu/privacy-policy/>), the cookies policy (<https://shift2zero-project.eu/cookies-policy/>) and the legal notice (<https://shift2zero-project.eu/legal-warning/>).

The webpage includes two forms gathering personal data from users: a contact form to manage user’s queries and an external sign-up form for users to subscribe to Shift2Zero Community of Interest (*for more information see section 5.1.1. Community of Interest*). For both forms EUT is the data controller. The data of the contact form will be transferred to partners involved in the project to better reply to the requests, while the users’ data of the community of interest will not be disclosed to third parties and will be processed by Mailchimp.

The website will also include specific forms to manage the registration of interest users to project events. The data included in these forms will be disclosed with the organising partner with the solely objective to register the users to the event and be able, afterwards, to send event materials to attendees.

4.2.8 Website accessibility

As part of the Shift2Zero website development and launch, EUT implemented the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines ([WCAG](https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/)) to ensure an inclusive and user-friendly experience. The main goal was to eliminate barriers that could affect accessibility, particularly focusing on removing obstacles that may prevent individuals with disabilities from effectively navigating and using the site. These guidelines were applied in various areas, such as using alternative text for non-text content (“Guideline 1.1 – Text Alternatives: Provide text alternatives for any non-text content, allowing it to be transformed into other formats like large print, braille, speech, symbols, or simpler language”); selecting accessible colours (“Guideline 1.4 – Distinguishable: Ensure users

can easily see and hear content, including separating foreground from background"); and designing the site structure ("Guideline 2.4 – Navigable: Provide ways to help users navigate, find content, and determine their location on the site").

4.3 Social Media

EUT oversees the management of Shift2Zero's social media channels and content. The project actively maintains a LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/shift2zero-project>) and a YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@Shift2ZeroProject>), which serves as a repository for video content.

A strategic social media plan has been implemented to achieve key performance indicators (KPIs), including the goal of surpassing 500 followers and effectively delivering project messages to target audiences. Each platform is tailored to engage specific groups:

- **LinkedIn:** Targets professionals such as researchers, industry experts, policymakers, and students.
- **YouTube:** Primarily serves as a content hub for all target groups, including citizens with an interest in the subject matter

Project partners will contribute to outreach efforts by sharing Shift2Zero content through their corporate and personal social media accounts, including X, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram.

All Shift2Zero social media communication will be in English. As the project coordinator, EUT will keep the European Commission informed about relevant content that may be shared via official EU social media channels, particularly those managed by the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Additionally, collaborations between Shift2Zero and related projects on social media will be encouraged whenever possible.

4.3.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a professional networking platform designed to foster knowledge sharing and career growth. It allows users to build communities around key initiatives, participate in discussions, and explore job opportunities.

Figure 33. Shift2Zero LinkedIn profile

At M1, the LinkedIn profile for Shift2Zero was launched to serve as a corporate timeline, connecting the research community, industry professionals, policymakers, and the broader public.

The page will feature content such as project updates, blog posts, articles, dissemination activities, meetings, and publications, both from the project itself and trusted third sources when applicable.

Figure 34. Examples of Shift2Zero LinkedIn posts

4.3.1.1 LinkedIn strategy

With the objective to implement and maintain an effective LinkedIn presence and engage the target audiences, the following content strategy has been defined:

- **Regular content sharing:** Posting and reposting at least two times per week, preferably on weekdays between 8 AM and 2 PM.
- **Use hashtags for visibility:**
 - **Project-specific:** #Shift2Zero #Shift2ZeroProject #S2Z
 - **Thematic:**
 - **Logistics and automotive industry:** #EULogistics #LogisticsInnovation #AutomotiveTech #AutomotiveInnovation #SmartMobility
 - **Sustainability:** #ZeroEmissionFuture #Decarbonisation #CleanTransport #GreenTransport #GreenTech #LowCarbonTransport #SustainableLogistics #Zeroemissionlogistics #ClimateAction #CarbonNeutralTransport #GreenMobility
 - **Funding-scheme related:** #HorizonEU #HorizonEurope #ResearchImpact #Innovation #EUFunding #EuropeanResearch
- **Tagging Partners:** Engaging with consortium partners by mentioning their LinkedIn accounts on the posts related to their activities: [Eurecat - Technology Centre](#), [Vrije Universiteit Brussel](#), [AIT Austrian Institute of Technology](#), [Alke Electric Vehicles](#), [GRUBER Logistics](#), [Transportøkonomisk institutt \(Norwegian Centre for Transport Research\)](#), [Bax Innovation](#), [ALICE, Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe \(ETP LOGISTICS\)](#), [Applus+ IDIADA](#), [Paxster AS](#), [Łukasiewicz – Poznański Instytut Technologiczny](#), [Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz – Przemysłowy Instytut Motoryzacji](#), [Michelin](#), [Institut für Kraftfahrzeuge \(ika\) - RWTH Aachen University](#), [Comune di Bologna](#), [Δήμος Θεσσαλονίκης - Municipality of Thessaloniki](#), [City of Wrocław](#), [Bruxelles Mobilité - Brussel Mobiliteit](#), [ITL \(Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation\)](#), [DIAKINISIS S.A.](#), [Clem'](#), [IVECO](#), [Bymiljøetaten i Bergen](#), [Brembo](#), [DHL Express Norge](#), [Cold Car Spa](#), [DPD](#) and [FIT Consulting srl](#).
- **Tagging EU funding agency: to acknowledge the funding received from the** [CINEA - European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency](#)
- **Audience engagement:** Beyond sharing Shift2Zero updates, actively engaging with related content—curating, reposting, liking, and commenting on relevant discussions.
- **Content mix:** Sharing website articles, project news, reports, and video materials.
- **Following related pages:** Enhancing visibility and networking by following and interacting with:
 - **Key EU projects and industry groups** such as: e.g. [2ZERO Partnership](#), [European Green Vehicles Initiative](#), [EARPA](#), [CIVITAS Initiative](#), [European Logistics Association](#), [EIT InnoEnergy](#), etc.
 - **Sister Projects:** relevant projects from the same call, touching upon similar topics:

4.3.1.2 LinkedIn analytics

Shift2Zero’s LinkedIn performance is tracked using LinkedIn Analytics, which provides insights into follower growth, post impressions, and engagement metrics. These indicators are monitored monthly to assess progress and update KPIs.

During the first three months (M1-M3), the Shift2Zero LinkedIn page gained **172 followers**. Over **16 posts** have been shared, generating **6K impressions**, **175 likes and reactions**, and **10 shares**.

The project’s LinkedIn page impact is monitored monthly using LinkedIn analytics. Data will be extracted monthly in the KPIs excel file available for all partners on the Sharepoint:

Figure 35. LinkedIn analytics tool

4.3.2 YouTube

The European Commission encourages the use of audiovisual content to make research project outcomes more accessible to the general public. In alignment with this recommendation, a YouTube channel was launched during M1 to host all project-related videos.

These videos will be shared on the project website and across Shift2Zero's social media platforms to ensure maximum reach and impact.

The Shift2Zero YouTube channel acts as a central video repository, with content aimed at scientists, policymakers, and the general public. Some videos may feature technical content designed for more specialized audiences.

Figure 36. View of Shift2Zero YouTube channel

4.3.2.1 YouTube strategy

Since the primary function of the Shift2Zero YouTube channel is to serve as a content repository, the following guidelines ensure consistency and optimisation when uploading videos:

- **Keyword optimisation:** Incorporate relevant keywords in titles and descriptions, such as *Shift2Zero project, Horizon EU, logistics, zero-emission future, mobility, green mobility, sustainability, logistics innovation, etc.*
- **Subtitles & accessibility:** Provide subtitles in the original video language and, where applicable, in partner languages to maximize reach and impact.
- **EU Funding acknowledgment:** Include the following statement in video descriptions: *The Shift2Zero project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Europe Programme: project num. 101192375*
- **Consistent branding:** Use standardised thumbnail templates to maintain a cohesive visual identity.
- **Regular updates:** Keep video content current and relevant.
- **Cross-promotion:** Share uploaded videos across LinkedIn, the project website, and partner channels to enhance visibility.

4.3.2.2 YouTube analytics

YouTube analytics will be used to track video performance, including views, watch time, and subscriber growth. Progress will be documented in interim reports, with monthly monitoring to evaluate KPIs accordingly.

4.3.3 Partners social media channels

Shift2Zero partners manage their own corporate social media accounts on LinkedIn, X, Instagram, BlueSky and Facebook, among other platforms. These channels will be used to promote the Shift2Zero project, with a goal of publishing at least **50 posts** as partners actively share updates on their initiatives and activities.

Project partners collectively have a strong online presence, with over **1,5 million followers on LinkedIn**, more than **753K on Instagram**, over **226K on X**, and **309K subscribers on YouTube** (as of April 2025).

Table 5. Partners social media channels

Partner	LinkedIn	Instagram	X
EUT	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurecat/	https://www.instagram.com/eurecat_org/#	@Eurecat_News
VUB	https://www.linkedin.com/school/vrije-universiteit-brussel/	https://www.instagram.com/vubrusssel/#	@VUBrusse
AIT	https://www.linkedin.com/company/austrian-institute-of-technology/	NA	@AITtomorrow2day
ALK	https://www.linkedin.com/company/alke-electric-vehicles/	https://www.instagram.com/alkeelectricvehicles/	@AlkeEVEhicles
GRU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/gruber-logistics/?originalSubdomain=it	https://www.instagram.com/gruberlogistics/	NA
TOI	https://www.linkedin.com/company/institute-of-transport-economics/posts/?feedView=all	NA	NA
BAX	https://www.linkedin.com/company/baxinnovation/posts/?feedView=all	NA	@BaxCompany
ALI	https://www.linkedin.com/company/alice-logistics/posts/?feedView=all	NA	NA
CER	https://www.linkedin.com/company/hellenic-institute-of-transport/posts/?feedView=all	https://www.instagram.com/hit.certh	@HitCerth
IDI	https://www.linkedin.com/company/applusiada/posts/?feedView=all	https://www.instagram.com/applusiada/	@ApplusiADA
IVE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ivecol/	https://www.instagram.com/iveco/	NA

MIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/michelin/	https://www.instagram.com/michelin/	@Michelin
LPIT	https://www.linkedin.com/company/lukasiewiczpit/	NA	@lukasiewiczpit
LPIM	https://www.linkedin.com/company/przemys%C5%82owy-institut-motoryzacji/	NA	@PIMOT_EU
COBO	https://www.linkedin.com/company/comune-di-bologna/posts/?feedView=all	https://www.instagram.com/comunedibologna/	@comunebologna
WRO	NA	https://www.instagram.com/portal_wroclawpl/	NA
THE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/-municipality-of-thessaloniki/	https://www.instagram.com/city.of.thessaloniki/	NA
BXL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sprb-bm/	https://www.instagram.com/bruxellesmobilite/	@MobirisFr
ITL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/itl-institute-for-transport-and-logistics-foundation-/?viewAsMember=true	NA	@FondazioneItl
DIA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/diakinesis-s-a/	NA	NA
BER	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bymiljoetaten-bergen/	https://www.instagram.com/bymiljoetaten_bergen/	NA
CLE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/clemmobi/	https://www.instagram.com/clem.mobi/	NA
DHL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/dhlexpress-norge/	https://www.instagram.com/dhlexpressnorge/	@DHLexpress
FIT	https://www.linkedin.com/company/fit-consulting-srl/posts/?feedView=all	NA	NA
COL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/coldcarspa/?originalSubdomain=it	https://www.instagram.com/coldcarspa?igsh=MTNkbjA4eWdhYm56cw==	NA
PAX	https://www.linkedin.com/company/paxster/	https://www.instagram.com/paxsterofficial/	NA
DPD	https://www.linkedin.com/company/dpd-polska-sp-z-o-o/	https://www.instagram.com/dpdpolska/	NA
BRE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/brembo/	https://www.instagram.com/brembo/	@BremboBrakes

4.3.3.1 Guidance for publishing about the project on social media

Partners publishing on social media are suggested to apply the following recommendations when communicating about Shift2Zero:

- Use of relevant project hashtags: #Shift2Zero, #Shift2ZeroProject or #S2Z.
- Mention / tag project's LinkedIn account when publishing in this specific platform.
- Mention project partners to increase the reach of the publications.
- Share links to project website / articles / materials.
- Communicate partners' role on the project.

Additionally, partners can also use the guidelines prepared, and detailed before, for the project's social media accounts, when publishing about the project.

4.4 Promotional and audio-visual materials

EUT is responsible for designing and producing a range of promotional materials, including printed, digital, and audiovisual content, to support dissemination activities at conferences, congresses, and project events.

An initial set of materials—comprising a roll-up banner, trifold brochure, general fact sheet, project presentation, and poster layout—will be developed by M5 to assist partners in their outreach efforts.

These materials will be designed for all target groups, highlighting the project's benefits and promoting market adoption. They will adhere to the project's visual identity guidelines (see section 4.1) and will be available in digital format for consortium members. Additionally, all materials will be publicly accessible on the project's website.

This set of materials will be updated at different stages of the project to include up-to-date information of the advances and results (at least at M42).

Rollups, trifold and poster

Figure 37. Designs proposals for Shift2Zero trifold and rollups

Figure 38. Designs and content proposal for Shift2Zero poster

Factsheets

General (version for academia and version for industry)

An A4 factsheet will be developed in M5, outlining the main objectives, expected results, and key project data, ensuring that relevant stakeholders receive targeted and valuable information.

Pilot activities

Throughout the project's duration, partners intend to create five technical factsheets based on pilot activities and results (M36 – M39). These factsheets will provide public information to interested stakeholders, summarizing the project's progress and main conclusions of the activity conducted in pilot sites.

EUT will develop a factsheet template aligned with the project's visual identity by M36. These factsheets will be published following the release of each deliverable and made available on the project's website. To enhance outreach and engagement, they will also be shared and promoted through the Shift2Zero LinkedIn account and the Zenodo Community.

4.4.1 Digital and printed materials produced

Poster layout

A poster layout has been created for all partners to use and adapt as needed. The document provides guidelines on how to organize content and information throughout the poster.

Figure 39. Shift2Zero poster layout

General presentation

To support communication for the Shift2Zero project, a PowerPoint presentation has been prepared. Each partner can add new slides and adapt the content according to their specific needs, the event being attended, and the target audience.

The core presentation offers a general overview of the project, including its main objectives, the consortium, expected impacts, and other relevant information.

Figure 40. View of some slides of the Shift2Zero general presentation

4.4.2 Audiovisual project materials

Over the course of the project, at least **five videos will be produced** between M1 – M42. These videos will highlight key milestones, showcase progress, and present final outcomes, helping to ensure wide dissemination of the project's insights and results.

Project conceptual video

A dedicated video will be created to clearly communicate the project's main objectives, along with its expected benefits and impact on industry, society, and the environment. Designed for a broad audience, the video will use accessible language to engage all stakeholders. Production will leverage 2D motion graphics, beginning in M6, with the final release planned for M8.

Pilot sites videos

These videos will showcase real-world applications of the project through pilot site demonstrations. Each video will present specific scenarios, highlighting how the project's solutions are implemented in practice, the challenges encountered, and the results achieved. The content will be tailored to provide clear, visual insights into the impact and scalability of the project across different contexts. These videos will be produced between M36 – M40.

Partners interviews

A series of short interview videos featuring project partners will be produced, each centred on key topics such as the project concept, solutions, methodology, scenarios, and other relevant themes. EUT will select these topics based on audience interest and will prepare guiding questions in advance to ensure the creation of focused and engaging video capsules. These interviews will be recorded during General Assemblies, with video production scheduled between M12 and M40 of the project timeline.

Final video with project results

The final video will showcase the key outcomes of the project, highlighting its results, practical applications, and the broad benefits delivered to academia, industry, and society. Produced by EUT, the video will combine dynamic visuals of the project's pilot sites with short interviews that provide insights from key partners.

Production will begin in M30, with a strong emphasis on selecting visuals that effectively capture the essence and impact of the project. Scheduled for release in M42, the video will serve as a compelling summary of the project's journey, achievements, and long-term value—crafted to resonate with a wide and diverse audience.

4.5 Media relations

Shift2Zero has defined a **comprehensive strategy to strengthen its engagement with the media sector**, with the objective to enhance visibility and raise awareness about the project's main objectives, results and expected impacts among its key target groups.

As part of this effort, a **minimum of four press releases** will be prepared and distributed to relevant EU media outlets, journalists specialising in different topics such as technology, logistics innovation, mobility, automotive, sustainability, decarbonisation, as well as related associations and their newsletters.

These press releases will highlight significant project achievements and developments, including research findings, key milestones, and participation in or organisation of events. Whenever possible, they will be linked to newsworthy initiatives to maximise media interest. Additionally, Shift2Zero will engage with journalists upon request for articles and media pieces related to the project's themes.

All press releases will be initially drafted in English and shared with project partners for feedback. Partners will also have the option to translate and adapt these articles into their language and disseminate them through their regional media channels.

Beyond consortium-wide press releases, **partners may develop country-specific or stakeholder-focused releases**. However, these will only be published after notifying the Project Coordinator and the Communication Leader (EUT), to ensure alignment with the overall communication strategy.

To enhance media coordination and visibility, a database of communication officers from all project consortium members has been compiled. This resource will streamline the review process, facilitate media distribution, and strengthen the project's presence across European media platforms.

In addition, a dedicated database of specialised media contacts will be developed, focusing on outlets and journalists covering technology, logistics, automotive, mobility and sustainability fields, among other topics related to Shift2Zero. Priority will be given to media outlets operating in the countries of consortium partners to maximise impact and outreach.

4.5.1 Relevant outlets

Over the course of the project, Shift2Zero aims to **secure the publication of at least 25 articles in general media outlets and 5 articles in specialised media**, with the goal of reaching over 30K EU citizens.

To maintain strategic alignment and maximise visibility, the publication timeline, choice of media outlets, and designated partners will be regularly assessed and discussed during consortium meetings. Media coverage will also be actively monitored to assess impact and engagement.

The primary goal is to engage a broad audience, including both academic and industrial professionals, with the project's key topics. A preliminary list of EU and international specialised media outlets identified as relevant for promoting Shift2Zero's outcomes is outlined in **Table X**.

Table 6. List of identified specialised media outlets

Outlet name	Website	Language
Automotive Manufacturing Solutions	https://www.automotivemanufacturingsolutions.com/	English
Automobil Produktion	https://www.automobil-produktion.de/	German
Green Car Reports	https://www.greencarreports.com/news/mobility	English
Science Daily (section on Automotive)	https://www.sciencedaily.com/news/computers_math/computer_modeling/	English
Automotive Manufacturing Solutions	https://www.automotivemanufacturingsolutions.com/	English
Industry Talks	https://industrytalks.es/	Spanish
Société des Ingénieurs de l'Automobile (SIA)	https://www.sia.fr/	French
The Logistics World	https://thelogisticsworld.com/	English
Il Giornale della Logistica	https://ilgiornaledellalogistica.it/	Italian
TIR	https://rivistatir.it/	Italian
Logistics Business Magazine	https://www.logisticsbusiness.com/	English
Fleet Europe	https://www.fleeteurope.com/en	English
Logistica Management	https://www.logisticamanagement.it/it/index.do	Italian
Logistica	https://www.logisticanews.it/	Italian
FACTS Magazine	https://www.factsmagazine.co.uk/	English
Logistics Business Magazine	https://www.logimat-messe.de/en/logistics-business-magazine	English
Transportation & Logistics International	https://tlimagazine.com/	English

Trasporto Europa	https://www.trasportoeuropa.it/english/news-from-the-world-of-transport-and-logistics-14-april-2025/	Italian
Logistics Management	https://www.logistics-management.gr/	Greek
Anlegg & Transport	https://www.at.no/	Norwegian
Logistikk Inside	https://www.logistikkinside.no/	Norwegian
Moderne Transport	https://www.mtlogistikk.no/	Norwegian
NLF Magasinet	https://lastebil.no/Aktuelt/NLF-Magasinet/Om-NLF-Magasinet	Norwegian
Transportmagasinet	https://www.transportmagasinet.dk/	Norwegian
Transport & Logistik	https://transportmesse.no/	Norwegian
Tungt.no	https://www.tungt.no/	Norwegian
Yrkesbil	https://www.yrkesbil.no/	Norwegian
Yrkestrafikk	https://ytf.no/yrkestrafikk	Norwegian

4.5.2 Press releases planning

Press releases will be issued in alignment with the progress of work packages (WPs), showcasing key deliverables and milestones achieved throughout the project.

The first press release, titled “*European consortium to invest €12 million in new designs and functionalities for electric commercial vehicles*”, is planned to be published in M5 (May 2025) and translated into multiple partner language and contexts.

Shift2Zero press releases will be prepared and distributed to both general and scientific media outlets. In the forthcoming months, the press release schedule will follow the plan in *Table 7*.

Table 7. Press releases plan

Month	Press release topic
M5	Initial press release (general information about the project, its main objectives and expected results, the consortium, etc.)
M30	Presenting project achievements and innovations, focused on new vehicle concepts (based on part of MS4)
M39	Shift2Zero economic, environmental, society & safety impact and introducing new results (based on MS5)
M42	Final Shift2Zero press release

5. Dissemination Plan

5.1 Rising awareness and creating bi-directional communities

5.1.1 Community of interest

A dedicated community of interest around the Shift2Zero project will be established through direct mailing to engage stakeholders interested in tracking the project's progress and participating in relevant events. This initiative aims to enhance the reach and impact of communication and dissemination efforts, with a goal of **building a community of at least 300 members**.

If necessary, community members may also be consulted for feedback and input on the outcomes of various Work Packages (WPs). To facilitate engagement, the Shift2Zero project will leverage email marketing to reach stakeholders who subscribe via a form integrated into the project's website.

Throughout the project, a minimum of **six newsletters** will be distributed and **2 contributions to relevant external newsletters** (e.g. CIVITAS newsletter) will be conducted.

Table 8. Newsletters calendar

Month	Topic
M6	First newsletter
M12	2 nd newsletter
M18	3 rd newsletter
M24	4 th newsletter
M36	5 th newsletter
M42	6 th newsletter

Additionally, **targeted email campaigns will be created to share key project updates**, including announcements about webinars, workshops, and other events. These campaigns will also play a crucial role in promoting the Shift2Zero final event, ensuring broad stakeholder engagement and participation.

Mailchimp is the email platform selected for distributing project-specific updates and information. This tool simplifies the creation of diverse newsletters and provides easy options for sharing them on social media.

It is recommended to use Mailchimp as the email platform for distributing project-specific updates and information. Mailchimp simplifies the creation of diverse newsletters and provides easy options for sharing them on social media.

5.1.1.1 Audience recruitment

Subscribers will be gradually acquired throughout the project via a sign-up form (https://cutt.ly/Shift2Zero_Communityofinterest), which has been featured on the project website's homepage and promoted through social media channels. All partners will be encouraged to expand the community by sharing dedicated emails and communication

materials within their networks. Additionally, event participants will be invited to join, further increasing the subscriber base.

The sign-up form complies with GDPR regulations, linking to the newsletter’s privacy policy and informing users of their right to unsubscribe at any time. Subscriptions and unsubscriptions will be automatically managed through Mailchimp, which will also facilitate email distribution.

Mailchimp will act as the data processor for Shift2Zero, ensuring that all data collected via the sign-up form is used exclusively to provide project-related information. Under no circumstances will subscriber data be shared with third parties unless legally required.

Through its newsletters, Shift2Zero aims to engage key stakeholder groups, including academia, industry, and society. Each group will receive tailored messages to maximize relevance and impact.

Figure 41. Shift2Zero sign-up form

5.1.1.2 Content & Analytics

The Communication Manager of the project (EUT) will be the main responsible of the newsletters’ content, with contributions from all project partners. Before each issue is published, partners will be contacted to provide insights and inputs, such as updates on project tasks, articles or upcoming events.

The content produced will be aligned with project milestones and activities, with each issue including references to Horizon Europe and contact information (email, website link, and social media).

Mailchimp will track analytics for newsletters and email campaigns, including open rates and click-through rates. These statistics will be reviewed three days after each newsletter is sent, allowing insights to be used to refine content and enhance the effectiveness of future communications.

5.2 Training and knowledge transfer activities

5.2.1 Technical webinars

Throughout the project's execution, various webinars will be organised to showcase research results and demonstrate the innovative solutions developed.

These webinars will primarily target a specific group of participants but will also be open to other invited companies. Partners may propose additional participants to broaden discussions, share results, explore next steps, and align development efforts with industry needs. This makes the workshops a crucial tool for ensuring that the project meets the requirements of its intended stakeholders.

Addressed stakeholders of the webinars are:

- Logistics and automotive sector
- Researchers working on project-related topics
- Advisory board members
- Representatives from similar projects

If necessary, an initial introductory webinar will be held to provide background information, introduce project objectives, and clarify expected outcomes. This session will also serve to generate interest and encourage participation in subsequent project events.

Webinars will be announced through the project's communication channels, including the website, social media, and the Shift2Zero mailing list. Sessions will be recorded and made available on the project's YouTube channel.

Details on the leading partner for each workshop and tentative dates are provided below:

Table 9. Calendar of proposed webinars

Proposed topic	Leading partner	Approximate date
Webinar #1: (based on WP3 results) Transforming user needs into next-gen vehicle designs: bridging requirements with innovation	EUT	M24
Webinar #2: (based on WP4 results) From prototype to reality: integrating and testing new functionalities in vehicle concepts	IDI, with support from ALK	M35
Webinar #3: (based on WP5 & WP6 results) Optimising eLCV operations: Simulation, Real-Life Demonstrations, and Evaluation	CERTH, GRU	M40
Webinar #4: (based on WP7 results) Evaluating Sustainability: Impact Assessment, LCA, and TCO in vehicle developments	TOI	M41

This preliminary calendar is subject to review and updates as needed, with adjustments to titles, dates, or topics to align with the evolving needs of the project. Additionally, new webinar proposals may be incorporated.

5.2.2 Pilot site visits

As part of the project's execution, **a series of site visits have been planned to evaluate the progress and outcomes of the pilot activities**. These visits are crucial for gaining direct insights into the implementation of the developed solutions and ensuring alignment with project objectives.

The **four pilot site visits and the macro-pilot site visit** will offer a unique opportunity to observe the broader application of the project's innovations in a full-scale operational environment. The visits will provide valuable insights into the viability and impact of the proposed solutions when implemented at a larger scale, enabling a more robust evaluation of their commercial and industrial potential.

Each visit will involve key project stakeholders (ST1 – 7), including researchers, engineers, and representatives from the involved industry partners, to ensure comprehensive feedback is gathered.

The site visits will be conducted at various stages of the project to track progress, identify challenges, and make necessary adjustments to the development process. These visits will also facilitate direct interaction between the project team and stakeholders, allowing for a collaborative approach to problem-solving and optimisation. Additionally, the findings and lessons learned from these visits will be documented and shared with the wider project team, ensuring continuous improvement throughout the project lifecycle.

In summary, the **4 pilot and 1 macro-pilot site visits** will provide critical feedback, demonstrate the real-world application of project solutions, and ensure the project is on track to meet its objectives and industry requirements.

5.2.3 Training courses and activities

Shift2Zero partners will integrate the acquired knowledge into existing training programs during and after the project. This will enable the transfer of expertise to companies, research centres, and European SMEs working in the project's focus areas, while also disseminating project results to the scientific, educational, and business communities. These efforts will help pave the way for future exploitation of the project's outcomes.

The training activities will target both the academic/scientific community and industry professionals. Additionally, these activities will involve project partners' organisations, facilitating horizontal knowledge transfer within the consortium.

The training will be delivered in various formats, including the incorporation of project results and materials into undergraduate, master's, and PhD programs, specialised courses, open days, and online tutorials, among others.

Training activities will be planned during the second and third years of the project, led mainly by academia partners (VUB, TOI, CERTH and RWTH) and research centres (EUT, AIT, LPIT, LPIM, ITL) within the consortium.

5.2.4 Final event

At the conclusion of the Shift2Zero project (M42), a final public event will be held to showcase the project's results to key stakeholders, including representatives from academia, research institutions, and industry – ranging from SMEs to large corporations within the mass-market logistics innovation field. The consortium will determine whether to host the event in one of the partner countries or align it with a major international congress or conference.

The target is to attract approximately 100 participants, including representatives from leading specialised media outlets. The event will be open to the public and promoted widely through Shift2Zerp and partner communication channels, with personalised invitations sent to key contacts within each partner's network.

ALICE will lead the organisation of the event, as Urban Logistics Innovation Day, with the collaboration of EUT as communication and dissemination manager, and the active support from all partners.

5.3 Scientific publications

Reports and outcomes from project activities will be published in scientific journals relevant to the project's fields. At least **five peer-reviewed journal publications are planned during the project period**. However, since the emergence of results and their technical maturity cannot be precisely scheduled, the timeline for these publications will remain flexible. EUT will oversee this process, aligning it with the work package plan.

During periodic meetings of WP leaders, significant results will be discussed, suitable journals will be selected, and publication timelines will be determined in collaboration with project partners. Journals will be chosen based on their relevance to the research topics.

Project partners will **ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications**. This will be achieved through gold open access (publisher-provided, free online access upon publication) whenever possible and/or green open access via an online repository (e.g., OpenAIRE or Zenodo) to guarantee long-term preservation and availability.

A dedicated **Shift2Zero Zenodo community** will be created to host all project-related research publications. Moreover, publications will be shared on researchers' ResearchGate profiles when applicable.

An initial list of open-access journals suitable for publishing Shift2Zero results has been identified as follows:

Table 10. List of identified journals

Journal name	Link
Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/transportation-research-part-a-policy-and-practice
Transportation Research Part B: Methodological	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/transportation-research-part-b-methodological
Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/transportation-research-part-d-transport-and-environment
Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/transportation-research-part-e-logistics-and-transportation-review

European Journal of Operational Research	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/european-journal-of-operational-research
ATZ – Springer Professional	https://www.springerprofessional.de/en/atz-worldwide/4980380
Applied Ergonomics	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/applied-ergonomics
Safety Science	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/safety-science
World Electric Vehicle Journal	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/wevj
International Journal of Electric and Hybrid Vehicles	https://www.inderscience.com/jhome.php?jcode=ijehv
IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=6979
EURO Journal on Transportation and Logistics (EJTL)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/euro-journal-on-transportation-and-logistics
International Journal of Shipping and Transport Logistics (IJSTL)	https://www.inderscience.com/jhome.php?jcode=ijstl
Journal of Sustainable Development of Transport and Logistics	https://jsdtl.sciview.net/index.php/jsdtl
Logistics	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/logistics

On the other hand, partners will consider the submission of papers to the **Open Research Europe**, an innovative open access publishing platform offering rapid publication and open peer review.

5.4 Participation to conferences, fairs & exhibitions

Active participation in national and international conferences, congresses and workshops is crucial for transferring the knowledge gained throughout the Shift2Zero project. A diverse array of events, including conferences, fairs, congresses and exhibitions, are ideal platforms for showcasing and publishing the project's findings, particularly in areas such as logistics innovation, sustainable mobility, and automotive decarbonisation, among others.

Through engagement in academic and industrial events, Shift2Zero partners will establish valuable connections with key players in the automotive sector, including OEMs, Tier 1 and Tier 2 suppliers, as well as fellow researchers.

Dissemination efforts will primarily focus on the countries of the project partners. Additionally, partners will explore opportunities to attend relevant events in other European nations, targeting communities that align with the project's objectives, particularly within academia and the sustainable transport and automotive sectors.

Participation in these events will be discussed during WP-leader meetings, and an Excel file in the SharePoint folder is available for partners to record their planned activities or identify any upcoming events of interest.

A non-exhaustive list of preliminary key events identified as relevant for disseminating the project's activities and outcomes is provided in Table 11. This list will be regularly updated by the partners.

Table 11. Preliminary list of identified events relevant for Shift2Zero

EVENT NAME	TYPE	DATES NEXT EDITION	CITY	COUNTRY
<u>Workshop</u> “Lightening the Load: Integrating Light Cargo Vehicles in Cities” by the International Transport Forum – ATTENDED	Workshop	April 2025	Online	Online
<u>ITS European Congress</u>	Congress	May 2025	Seville	Spain
<u>International Symposium on Sustainable Logistics</u>	Conference	May 2025	Mersin	Türkiye
<u>Cities Mission Conference</u> “Harnessing City Successes: Advancing Climate Action for 2030”	Conference	May 2025	Vilnius	Lithuania
<u>Transport Logistic Munich 2025</u>	Fair	June 2025	Munich	Germany
<u>11th International Physical Internet Conference</u> <u>AI-empowered Physical Internet</u>	Conference	June 2025	Hong Kong	China
<u>SIL Expo Barcelona</u>	Exhibition	June 2025	Barcelona	Spain
<u>Transportmessa på Gardermoen</u>	Conference	August 2025	Gardermoen	Norway
<u>EARPA’s FORM Forum</u>	Conference	October 2025	Brussels	Belgium
<u>ALICE Logistics Innovation Summit</u>	Conference	October 2025	Brussels	Belgium
<u>Leaders in Logistics Last Mile</u>	Congress	October 2025	London	UK
<u>Global Mobility Call</u>	Conference	October 2025	Madrid	Spain
<u>Logistics Supply Chain</u>	Conference	October 2025	Athens	Greece
<u>Annual POLIS Conference</u>	Conference	November 2025	Utrecht	The Netherlands
<u>Zerokonferansen</u>	Conference	November 2025	Oslo	Norway
<u>Smart City Expo</u>	Exhibition	November 2025	Barcelona	Spain
<u>Urban Logistics Innovation Day (URBANE final event)</u>	Conference	November 2025	Barcelona	Spain
<u>RTR Conference</u>	Conference	February 2026	Brussels	Belgium
<u>Automotive Logistics & Supply Chain Europe</u>	Conference	March 2026	Kameha Grand Bonn	Germany

<u>LogiMotion</u>	Exhibition	April 2026	TBD	Dubai
<u>Transport Research Arena (TRA)</u>	Conference	May 2026	Budapest	Hungary
<u>European Mobility Expo</u>	Exhibition	June 2026	Paris	France
<u>World Conference on Transport Research</u>	Conference	July 2026	Toulouse	France
<u>Global supply chain & logistics summit</u>	Conference	November 2026	Frankfurt	Germany
<u>ITS European Congress</u>	Congress	During 2026	TBD	TBD
<u>SAE International World Congress</u>	Congress	During 2026	TBD	TBD
<u>Annual Cities Mission</u>	Conference	During 2026	TBD	TBD
<u>EARPA's FORM Forum</u>	Conference	October 2027	Brussels	Belgium
<u>ALICE Logistics Innovation Summit</u>	Conference	October 2027	Brussels	Belgium
<u>Transport Research Arena (TRA)</u>	Conference	May 2028	TBD	TBD
<u>12th International Congress on Transportation Research (ICTR)</u>	Conference	Sep 2025	Thessaloniki	Greece

6. Clustering strategy

Clustering activities, included within the subtask ST8.3.3., have the objective to **create synergies with running and future initiatives and projects** for knowledge transfer on key topics, increasing visibility and fostering collaborations.

During the execution of the Shift2Zero project, the consortium will maintain regular contact with coordinators of related projects, relevant industry associations, companies, and European institutions operating in the project's focus areas.

Initial synergies between Shift2Zero and other groups have already begun through participation in relevant events and working groups organised or attended by the stakeholders outlined in the sections below. In addition, project partners will engage with initiatives promoted by these entities and contribute Shift2Zero-related content to association newsletters and publications, where possible.

To further enhance collaboration and visibility, the following additional activities will be undertaken:

- **Contribute, upon invitation by the European Commission, to joint information and dissemination activities** that enhance the visibility of Shift2Zero and create synergies between Horizon Europe projects and the 2Zero partnership.

- **Engage in specific, active cooperation with relevant networks, initiatives, and projects**, with contributions from EUT, BAX, and ALL.
- **Participate in clustering activities with other projects**, including the establishment of a dedicated dissemination cluster with other EU-funded projects under the same topic.
- **Utilize European Commission communication channels** such as EU newsletters, CORDIS, and others to disseminate project outcomes.

Joint activities with sister projects and EU initiatives and platforms up to M4 include:

Table 12. Clustering and joint dissemination actions with projects, initiatives and platforms of interest

Date	Initiative / project	Activity description
February 2025	2Zero Partnership	Publication of the article “A warm welcome to the new 2Zero Partnership Projects: ePowerMove, NEVERFLAT, GEN1200, HiVEP, Enlighten, S4MILE, ARISE, FLEXMCS, MACBETH, TWIN-LOOP, CODE4EV, and Shift2Zero!” in the 2Zero website. See more information here
March 2025	2Zero Partnership	Inclusion of Shift2Zero information in the “Research projects list” section of the 2Zero website. See more information here .

6.1 Joint actions with liaison projects

Connections with other projects, initiatives, and knowledge hubs with complementary objectives are being actively pursued at national, European, and international levels. The goal is to **strengthen synergies while avoiding duplication of efforts in the dissemination of results**.

Collaborating with other projects and initiatives enables the pooling of resources, coordinated communication efforts, and a stronger collective voice when engaging with target audiences. These partnerships will also enhance visibility and maximise the impact of shared findings.

As part of this strategy, **a dissemination cluster will be established with other EU projects funded under the same topic**, creating a structured platform for coordinated outreach and knowledge exchange.

Table 13. Preliminary list of Shift2Zero liaison projects

Project	Short description
EMPOWER (ending December 2026)	The EMPOWER project aims to develop two flexible, modular, and scalable zero-emission heavy-duty vehicles (ZE HDV).
MINDED (ending December 2026)	MINDED is an innovative project dedicated to transforming road transport by developing a zero-emission, battery-electric IVECO e-daily minibus. The goal is to improve the vehicle’s range and performance while ensuring passenger comfort and reducing costs.
ZEFES (ending June 2026)	ZEFES is deploying 9 different long-haul truck configurations (BEV and FCEV) in various use cases covering important TEN-T corridors in Europe. The project addresses the decarbonisation of long-distance freight transport by demonstrating real-world applications with battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) across Europe.

URBANE (ending February 2026)	URBANE develops a Replication and Scale up Model for the wide and fast replication of successful PI-inspired smart green last mile delivery solutions, aiming at 20% reduction in CO ₂ emissions, by testing, among others electric cargo bikes and PVpowered vans.
DISCO (ending October 2026)	The DISCO project focuses on interconnected urban freight organisation and city planning, through data sharing and digitalization, based on a Physical Internet (PI) approach. DISCO will develop a federated European urban freight platform, for safe and smart voluntary data sharing on urban logistics and its urban space use.
MODI (ending March 2026)	The overall objective of MODI is to accelerate the introduction of connected, cooperative and automated mobility (CCAM) vehicles for logistics by demonstrations and to overcome barriers for the roll-out of automated transport systems and solutions in logistics.
ePowerMove (ending June 2028)	The ePowerMove concept is to develop a global energy-usage optimiser which brings together advanced technologies from charging infrastructure design and grid energy control, with a number of innovative and complementary elements to maximise the potential utilisation of individual innovations.
S4SMILE (ending June 2028)	S4MILE project aims to support the large-scale introduction of electric vehicles by simplifying the vehicle structure and integrating the next-generation solid-state cells into the vehicle structure based on a disruptive and innovative 'virtual' module-to-chassis concept (VM2C) based on large structural ALU casting and composite unibodies.
NEVERFLAT (ending June 2028)	NEVERFLAT aims to develop and demonstrate in real-life settings an innovative, efficient, and user-friendly pervasive low-cost smart bi-directional charging infrastructure for electric vehicles (EVs).
MACBETH (ending January 2029)	The MACBETH project will pilot the mass deployment of megawatt charging systems (MCS) at two demonstration sites in Europe. Aiming to electrify long-haul trucks, MACBETH will address technical, social, and economic challenges by developing MCS hubs along critical logistics corridors.
MED COLOURS (ending September 2026)	Mediterranean Collaborative Logistics for the Urban Space is a EU Project co-funded by the Interreg Euro-MED. MED COLOURS aims at upscaling to a new generation of urban logistics and planning enabling the transition to decarbonised and smart cities. By developing new Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans (SULPs), MED Cities will plan resilient, sustainable, integrated, and collaborative innovation-driven solutions for the Functional Urban Areas (FUAs). This would help reducing the negative impacts of freight and logistics activities.
MOBILAIR (ending August 2026)	MOBILAIR focuses on climate justice in the city of Thessaloniki and considers Air Quality Management and Sustainable Urban Mobility. MOBILAIR evaluates potential user-centric, data-driven Air Quality management measures, aiming to influence travelers' behavior towards environmentally friendly Urban Mobility choices. The project is funded by the ICLEI Action Fund Greece and google.org.
NetZeroCities (ending December 2027)	The project is a CSA to support the European Commission Mission for 100 Climate-neutral and Smart Cities by 2030 (the Cities Mission), seeking to accelerate Europe's climate action commitments as part of the European Green Deal, whose ambition is to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050.
GOLIA (ending June 2028)	GOLIA (Governing, Optimising and Leveraging Innovations proActively for shaping future proof holistic mobility system through data-driven and social optimum-led model), with the grant agreement number of 101201950, is a new project to create on an integrated, interdisciplinary and Adaptive Mobility Smart Governance Model, relying on data-based, social optimum-driven approach and inclusive policy making processes to ensure an adaptive, accessible and just mobility system.

6.2 Joint actions with EU clusters, associations and initiatives

ALICE, a consortium member of Shift2Zero, is a key association, playing a crucial role in the EU mobility and logistics policy dialogues. ALICE's membership covers many associations, such as ACEA, and EIT Urban Mobility. It is also a member of Expert Group on Urban Mobility (EGUM), 2Zero, ERTRAC.

Cooperation and synergies will be established with relevant initiatives and platforms, some of which are listed below:

Table 14. Initial list of identified clusters, associations and initiatives

Initiative	Brief description	Website
2Zero (several partners are members)	The Towards zero emission road transport (2Zero) is a co-programmed Partnership funded under the Horizon Europe programme and aiming at accelerating the transition towards zero tailpipe emission road mobility across Europe. Bringing together stakeholders from three different European Technology Platforms (ERTRAC, EPoSS and Smart Grids), the European Green Vehicles Initiative contributed to improving the energy efficiency of alternative powertrains in road transport.	www.2zeroemission.eu
EARPA (supports the Shift2Zero project which involves several members)	EARPA is the association of automotive R&D organisations. It brings together the most prominent independent R&D providers in the automotive sector throughout Europe.	www.earpa.eu
The Catalan Automotive Cluster (CIAC) (EUT is a member)	The Automotive Industry Cluster of Catalonia (CIAC) is a non-profit association open to companies operating in the automotive industry, that are based in Catalonia, and pursue R&D+i activities.	www.ciac.cat
ICLEI - The network of local governments from sustainability	ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability is a global network working with more than 2500 local and regional governments committed to sustainable urban development. Active in 125+ countries, we influence sustainability policy and drive local action for low emission, nature-based, equitable, resilient and circular development.	www.iclei.org
POLIS network	POLIS is the leading network of European cities and regions working together to develop innovative technologies and policies for local transport.	www.polisnetwork.eu
CIVITAS Initiative	The CIVITAS Initiative works to make sustainable and smart urban mobility a reality for all in Europe and beyond.	www.civitas.eu
ACEA – the European Automobile Manufacturers Association	The European Automobile Manufacturers' Association (ACEA) represents the 15 major Europe-based car, van, truck and bus makers. ACEA is a member of ALICE.	www.acea.be
CARA – European Cluster for Mobility Solutions	CARA supports the transformation of passenger and freight transport systems to meet the challenges of digitalisation and decarbonisation of means of transport. CARA is a member of ALICE.	www.cara.eu/en/ www.cara.eu/fr/
EACN – The European Automotive Cluster Network	The European Automotive Cluster Network EACN is the leading network of clusters active in the fields of automotive, transport and mobility in Europe. It has been initiated in 2017 by eight clusters and grew to reach today 24 clusters from 11 European countries.	www.eacn-initiative.eu/
CIRCOE – Conseil & Innovation en Logistique	CIRCOE is an innovation and technologies transfer centre specialized in transport and logistics based in Le Havre, Normandy, which aims at stimulating economic development.	www.en.circoe.com/
EIT Urban Mobility	EIT Urban Mobility is an initiative of the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT). Since January 2019 we have been working to encourage positive changes in the way people move around cities in order to make them more liveable places. We aim to become the largest European initiative transforming urban mobility. EIT Urban Mobility is a member of ALICE	www.eiturbanmobility.eu/

Clust-ER GreenTech	An association of companies, research centers, and training institutions from Emilia-Romagna and beyond, collaborating through an open innovation approach in the fields of energy and sustainable development.	https://greentech.clust-er.it/
COE SUFS	The Global Centre of Excellence for a Sustainable Urban Goods Distribution System (CoE-SUFS) is dedicated to researching solutions to give new momentum to sustainability and efficiency in the field of urban goods distribution	https://cite.rpi.edu/coe-sufs/
ALIS	The Association for Sustainable Intermodal Logistics is the reference association for the entire logistics, transport, and business services sector in Italy and Europe.	https://www.alis.it
SOS Logistica	The Association gathers and promotes the best practices in Green Logistics and Sustainable Mobility, developing projects, activities, and ecosystems aimed at raising awareness among client companies, public administrations, and final consumers about the value of these processes.	https://www.logisticasostenibile.org/
Hellenic Institute for Logistics Management	A non-profit organization founded in 1994 with the aim of strengthening the Greek Logistician profession and its connection with the European reality and European developments in the field of Supply Chain.	https://www.ilme.gr/
Freight Leaders Council	A private association which contributes to the development of an increasingly competitive, sustainable, and advanced logistics sector. Studies and initiatives result in opinions, evaluations, and guidelines aimed at institutions, industry professionals, and the general public.	https://www.freightleaders.org/
Greek Logistics Company	EEL constitutes the Scientific, non-profit organisation that promotes the interests and demands of the Logistics Market and represents the Greek logistician at all competent Institutions and Governmental Authorities, contributing significantly to the development of the entire sector.	https://eel.gr/en/
CLEPA - European Association of Automotive Suppliers	CLEPA is the voice of European automotive suppliers, representing over 3.000 companies which employ 5.000.000 employees.	www.clepa.eu
Open ENLoCC	The European Network of Logistics Competence Centers is an open network of regional logistics competence centres in the field of logistics, run by public authorities or similar bodies.	https://www.openenlocc.net/
ANCI	The National Association of Italian Municipalities represents and advocates for the interests of Italian municipalities at various levels of government. Among its various activities, it promotes sustainable urban logistics solutions, integrated with Smart City development and supports municipalities in reducing emissions and improving last-mile delivery in urban areas. Strong focus is placed on energy efficiency and the use of renewable sources in transport.	https://www.anci.it/struttura/area-innovazione-tecnologica/
Assologistica	Italian trade association representing logistics companies, general and cold storage warehouses, as well as port, interport, and airport terminal operators. Assologistica represents over 250 member companies.	https://www.assologistica.it/
Climate Neutral and Smart Cities	One of the EU Missions that focusses on transforming 100 EU cities into climate neutral examples	https://netzerocities.eu/

6.3 Stakeholder Advisory Board

A **Stakeholder Advisory Board** will be formed with the objective to involve high-level external international institutions from policy, research, and industry fields, including among others the European Automotive Research Partner Association (EARPA), the 2Zero Partnership, the Catalan Automotive Cluster (CIAC) and the network of local governments from sustainability (ICLEI), as well as relevant local and regional stakeholders.

The Stakeholder Advisory Board will provide input and feedback through workshops and focus groups, actively participating in project events and contributing to the co-creation of Shift2Zero solutions.

7. CDC activities calendar (M4 – M42)

Activity description	Apr-25	May-25	Jun-25	Jul-25	Aug-25	Sep-25	Oct-25	Nov-25	Dec-25	Jan-26	Feb-26	Mar-26	Apr-26
	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16
Rollup	X	X											
Poster	X	X											
Trifold	X	X											
General presentation	X	X											
Factsheet	X	X											
D8.1 Communication & Dissemination strategy	X												
First press release		X											
Website Resources pages		X	X	X	X	X							
Project conceptual video			X	X	X	X							
First newsletter			X										
Stakeholder Advisory Board establishment										X	X		
Promotion of the Community of Interest	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Second newsletter									X				
Partners interviews videos										X	X	X	X

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Activity description	May-26	Jun-26	Jul-26	Aug-26	Sep-26	Oct-26	Nov-26	Dec-26	Jan-27	Feb-27	Mar-27	Apr-27	May-27
	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Promotion of the Community of Interest	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Third newsletter		X											
Partners interviews videos	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Fourth newsletter								X					
First technical webinar								X					
Training activities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Technical factsheet about pilot sites													X

Activity description	Jun-27	Jul-27	Aug-27	Sep-27	Oct-27	Nov-27	Dec-27	Jan-28	Feb-28	Mar-28	Apr-28	May-28	Jun-28
	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42
Partners interviews videos	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Training activities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Technical Factsheet about pilot sites	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Pilot sites videos							X	X	X	X	X	X	
Second webinar						X							
Fifth newsletter							X						
Pilot sites visits							X	X	X	X	X		
Third press release										X			
Third webinar											X		
Fourth webinar												X	

Final event														X
Final video	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Final newsletter														X
Final press release														X